

Administrative Styles of School Heads and Teacher Morale in Public Secondary Schools of Davao del Norte Division

Jessa Mae B. Degamo

Abstract. The study explored the relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale in public secondary schools of Davao del Norte Division. Also, it investigated the association of the involved variables and the domains of administrative styles of school heads that significantly influence the teacher morale. With the use of probability sampling, 190 public secondary teachers were selected as the respondents. Utilizing the descriptive-correlational survey method, the data collated were analyzed through the use of Mean, Product-Moment correlation and Regression Analysis. Results revealed that there was an extensive administrative style and a very extensive teacher morale. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between administrative style of school heads and teacher morale. Moreover, all domains of administrative styles, namely, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision were found to have significantly influence the teacher morale. Based on the findings, it was further suggested that higher officials in the Department of Education may craft programs and interventions that would reinforce the administrative styles of school heads and would pave a way to boost the morale of the teachers. Moreover, future researchers may further explore the involved variables considering other factors and research methods.

KEY WORDS

1. Administrative Styles 2. Teacher Morale 3. Davao del Norte Division

Date Received: May 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: June 15, 2025 — Date Published: July 12, 2025

1. Introduction

Teachers' morale is the collective feelings and attitudes of an individual and a group related to their duties, responsibilities, and goals; the state of mind of a teacher with respect to their work. Teachers who have high morale are more likely to motivate students to learn in the classroom, to ensure the implementation of educational reforms and to develop feelings of satisfaction and fulfillment. However, problems about teachers' morale are evident. In fact, it is believed that teachers with low morale are unhappy and dissatisfied with their profession. In addition, those schools who have decreased teachers' morale, students showed less achievement. When the teacher's morale is low, then it results in a decrease in students' achievement due to their sick state of mind. In USA, a survey highlights troubling teacher morale issues. Teachers would think twice about encouraging their younger selves to pursue education. Most teachers would not choose a teaching career again and nearly half of teachers say poor mental health is impacting their work. In fact, more than one-third (35 percent) of educators are con-

sidering leaving the profession altogether (Ascione, 2023). In Africa, Mboweni and Taole (2022) revealed that teacher morale was low. Teachers have identified school climate factors such as inappropriate professional development activities and violence as threats to their morale. Furthermore, a lack of parental involvement in the affairs of the school was regarded as a setback by teachers. Holden (2017) as cited by Shavuka and Shikongo (2020) disclosed that in China negative factors affect teacher morale at an international school. These negative factors included lack of recognition for extra duties, personality of a leader, and leadership transition. This shows that it is very important to maintain positive teacher morale. In the Philippines, schools in our nation are facing a critical period with low teacher morale, job-related stress, teachers leaving the profession, and recruitment problems continuing to grow over the last few years. In Bulacan, educational specialists claim that teacher morale has suffered from responsibility stresses and constrained competence (Caoc, 2022). Viaro and Ancho (2020) also mentioned that a large number of issues and challenges faced by teachers has taken a toll on their morale, leading to low teacher effectiveness and low commitment. The teaching career still has a reputation for being an underpaid and seldom recognized profession. Reports have also indicated the existence of several issues including corruption within the education system, insufficient teaching and learning facilities, relevant training on curriculum content and pedagogies, and most provisions of the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (Republic Act No. 4670) have yet to be enforced (Tarraya, 2023). In Davao City, there are principals in Davao City who are shabbily treating their subsidiary teachers because of their greed, chiefly embezzling the funds of Parents-Teachers Association. This causes low morale amongst the teachers and the shout of parents to seek capable and dependable principals (Ingay, 2019).

In Davao del Norte, the researcher observed that teachers experienced low morale due to heavy workloads, insufficient resources, and limited opportunities for professional growth. These factors lead to burnout, decreased motivation, and a lack of enthusiasm for teaching, ultimately affecting the quality of education and overall school performance. Apparently, so many issues regarding teacher morale need to be addressed. While numerous studies explored teacher morale as a critical factor influencing educational outcomes, there remained a noticeable gap in understanding how the administrative styles of school heads specifically impacted this variable. Existing research predominantly focused on general factors affecting teacher morale, such as workload, compensation, and professional development opportunities, without adequately addressing the nuanced role of administrative leadership. The link between distinct administrative styles and their direct and indirect effects on teacher morale was underexplored, particularly in diverse educational contexts. This lack of focused inquiry limited the ability of policymakers and school leaders to implement tailored strategies that effectively enhance teacher well-being and performance. Motivated by this gap in existing research, the researcher explored the nuances of administrative styles of school heads and its intersection with the teacher morale, focusing specifically on public secondary schools of Davao del Norte Division. The primary goal was to scrutinize the correlation between these two variables. Also, it investigated the domains of administrative styles of school heads that significantly influence teacher morale. The study of administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale was socially relevant as it highlighted the leadership-employee dynamic in the education sector, which profoundly influence teacher morale. High teacher morale contributes to better teaching outcomes. In this academic journey, the researcher aimed to share the findings

of this study through academic journals, conferences, and professional development workshops for educators and school administrators. Additionally, policymakers and stakeholders could access summarized results through education forums and policy briefs to inform leadership training and school governance strategies. This ensured the practical application of the research to enhance the quality of education at both local and national levels.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—This study examines the relationship between the administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. The six indicators of administrative style are initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, decision-making, and critique (Al-Omari, 2013), while the three indicators of teacher morale are rationality, belongingness, and identification (Brion, 2015).

1.1.1. Administrative Styles of School Heads—Effective school administration plays a pivotal role in educational success, relying on leadership that manages resources and policies efficiently (Ada Mkpa, 2020; Imakpokmwan et al., 2022). Administrative styles influence staff motivation, resource use, and organizational performance (Olayisade Awolusi, 2021). School administrators must be strategic, visionary, and collaborative, often balancing multiple duties (Krasniqi, 2021; Klinck et al., 2023; Shah, 2023).

1.1.2. Initiative—Initiative reflects proactive leadership involving creativity, problem-solving, and strategic foresight (Kilic, 2021; Kumar et al., 2024). It fosters autonomy and innovation in schools (Gorgijevski et al., 2022; Yalcinkaya et al., 2021). Characteristics include perseverance, risk-taking, and alignment with organizational goals (Ikhide et al., 2024; Fay, 2022; Iqbal et al., 2021; Doygunel Koprulu, 2022).

1.1.3. Inquiry—Inquiry-based leadership integrates data literacy, reflective thinking, and collaborative decision-making (Liujk et al.,

2019; Amels et al., 2020; Vermeulen et al., 2020). It emphasizes creating a culture of inquiry, enhancing school improvement and instructional quality (Graves, 2020; Aldridge, 2023; Schildkamp, 2019). Leaders must model open-mindedness and data-informed strategies (Day et al., 2020; Henderson Corry, 2020; Maynooth, 2022).

1.1.4. Advocacy—School leaders and counselors advocate for student needs by collaborating with educators, promoting equity, and shaping policy (Lane et al., 2022; Hollincheck et al., 2024). Effective advocacy involves teamwork, clear communication, and leadership in implementing support systems for student well-being (Raymond et al., 2024; Jaffer, 2022; Reese, 2021).

1.1.5. Conflict Management—Conflicts in schools, if well-managed, can lead to positive change. Effective leadership mitigates conflict through active listening, compromise, and creating supportive environments (Osondu Victor, 2022; Hussain et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2020). Job satisfaction improves when leaders manage conflict constructively and recognize teachers' contributions (Imperial et al., 2023; Marquez, 2023; Wainana et al., 2020).

1.1.6. Decision-Making—Decision-making in school administration requires flexibility, analysis, and alignment with educational goals (Anjum, 2022; Qamar Rashid, 2020; Greene, 2020). Leaders adapt their styles depending on the situation and staff cooperation (Almazan, 2024; Shaked, 2019). Participatory decision-making enhances staff morale and institutional growth (David et al., 2021; Yambo, 2022; Motloung Lew, 2023).

1.1.7. Critique—Constructive feedback from administrators is key to teacher improvement and school success. Effective feedback must be relevant, data-informed, and tailored to instructional needs (Congcong Caingcoy, 2020; Tay Lam, 2022; Goffin et al., 2023). Principals must be instructional leaders, capable of

evaluating, mentoring, and developing teacher performance (Balyer Ozcan, 2020; Mughal et al., 2023; Zrien David, 2023).

1.1.8. Teacher Morale—Teacher morale involves job satisfaction, enthusiasm, and alignment with organizational goals (Kapoor, 2023; Converso et al., 2019). High morale boosts student learning, while low morale leads to burnout and decreased performance (Ilrath Govender, 2021; Mutesasira Bantwini, 2022). Contributing factors include workload, professional development, resources, and school climate (Mboweni Taole, 2022; Werang, 2023).

Rationality refers to alignment between job expectations and school goals. Teachers use bounded rationality to simplify complex environments and make instructional decisions (Robbins, 2022; Erceg et al., 2022; Geven et al., 2021).

Belongingness emphasizes acceptance, support, and collegiality. A strong sense of belonging enhances well-being and commitment (Allen et al., 2021; Arslan, 2021; Donlon et al., 2020). School climate and supportive leadership are key contributors (Haynsworth, 2021; Yip, 2024).

Identification entails alignment between personal and organizational values. It strengthens commitment, shapes professional identity, and boosts performance (O'Neill, 2023; Dag Akdag, 2023; Wong Liu, 2022). Teachers' identities evolve with context and experience (Lobaugh, 2024; Jackson et al., 2022).

1.1.9. Link Between Administrative Style and Teacher Morale—Supportive leadership through recognition, inclusion in decision-making, and visibility fosters teacher commitment and morale (Mangin, 2021; Buenvenida Tamayo, 2020). Teachers thrive when they feel respected, included, and trusted (Erichsen Reynolds, 2020; Roberts, 2022; Qaralleh, 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—The accumulated and pertinent literature and studies substantiate the

connection between the variables in this study. Administrative styles of school heads significantly influence teacher morale, shaping both the school environment and the overall satisfaction and motivation of teachers. Additionally, the administrative style adopted by school heads plays a critical role in fostering teacher morale, which in turn affects teacher performance, job satisfaction, and student outcomes. Effective school leadership, therefore, involves adopting administrative styles that prioritize open communication, trust, and collaboration to support teachers' well-being and cultivate a positive, motivated workforce. The presentations and discussions of these related studies have contributed essential insights that will enrich the professional discourse concerning the study's findings.

1.3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—This study was primarily grounded in the Transformational Leadership Theory by Burns (1978) as cited in Greimel et al. (2022). According to Burns, transforming leadership is a process in which leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation. According to Burns, the transforming approach creates significant change in the life of people and organizations. It redesigns perceptions and values, and changes expectations and aspirations of employees. Unlike in the transactional approach, it is not based on a "give and take" relationship, but on the leader's personality, traits and ability to make a change through example, articulation of an energizing vision and challenging goals. Ilrath and Govender (2021) cited that school leaders have even the power to influence teacher morale. Taylor (2019) emphasized that school leaders administrative styles affect the attitudes of teachers working with them; morale of teachers should be kept at high place as teachers' high morale is a means of achieving better efficiency. In a school system there exist various kinds of leadership with their own leadership styles that

influence teacher morale. Educational management always stresses that school administrators shall be able to do and accomplish their work as well as to satisfy the needs of teachers. Teachers' moral affects proportionally the quality of the service they render. Teachers have a myriad of roles included in their job. In the context of this study, transformational leadership theory is highly relevant to the administrative styles of school heads and their influence on teacher morale, as it emphasizes the ability of leaders to inspire, motivate, and support their teams toward shared goals. By fostering a vision of growth, collaboration, and innovation, transformational school heads create an environment where teachers feel valued, empowered, and professionally fulfilled. This leadership style prioritizes open communication, recognition of achievements, and personal development, addressing both the emotional and professional needs of teachers. As a result, it enhances teacher morale by building trust, reducing stress, and promoting a sense of purpose and community within the school, ultimately leading to improved teacher satisfaction and performance. Another theory that supported this study is the Path-Goal Leadership Theory by House (1971) as cited in Olowoselu et al. (2019). Path-goal leadership theory aims to clarify the practice of how leaders are able to assist their followers along the path to their objectives. This theory includes four different approaches of leadership behaviour, which were directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented leadership. Directive leadership provides psychological structure for employees. While supportive leadership is based on employees' satisfaction. Whereas participative leadership is when leader encourages employee to participate in decision making. While achievement-oriented leadership is the leadership behaviour that sets clear and achievable target or goal for employee to achieve (Olowoselu et al., 2019). In the context of this study, the theory is relevant to the admin-

istrative styles of school heads and its impact on teacher morale as it focuses on how leaders can facilitate the achievement of goals by clarifying paths, removing obstacles, and providing necessary support. A school head employing this leadership style adapts their approach to meet the varying needs of teachers, ensuring they feel supported and empowered in their roles. By addressing challenges that hinder performance and offering clear guidance and resources, this approach fosters a sense of confidence and accomplishment among teachers. This alignment of leadership actions with teachers' needs and expectations enhances their job satisfaction, motivation, and overall morale, contributing to a positive and productive school environment. Herzberg's Two Factor Theory also supported the direction of this study. Herzberg et al. (1959 cited in Nickerson, 2025) provided the theory of motivation that human work needs originate from motivation factors and hygiene factors or factors for persistence, or the two-factor theory, which are factors that directly produce motivation and work morale. Depending on the organization's morale, management is accountable for the teacher's loyalty, sense of responsibility, and work productivity. If a teacher is a good member of the school, he or she will certainly exhibit desirable behaviors in order to accomplish duties effectively. In contrast, if a school lacks incentives, motivation, and morale in practice, its performance will decline, and its teachers will become bored and inefficient (Kanthap, 2022). Therefore, morale is a significant variable, as it is directly associated with effective and efficient school administration. In this study, the theory is relevant to the administrative styles of school heads and its influence on teacher morale as it highlights the dual role of hygiene factors and motivators in job satisfaction. School heads can enhance teacher morale by addressing hygiene factors such as providing fair compensation, fostering positive working conditions, and ensuring job security. At the same time,

they can motivate teachers by focusing on factors that bring satisfaction, including recognition, opportunities for professional growth, and a sense of achievement. By balancing these elements, school heads create an environment where teachers feel both supported in their basic needs and inspired to excel, leading to higher morale and improved performance. Figure 1 shows below the conceptual model of the study. It focuses on administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. The independent variable is the administrative styles of school heads. It has 6 indicators namely: initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decisions, and critique (Al-Omari, 2013). In this study, initiative refers to the proactive approach leaders take to identify and implement improvements, motivate staff, and foster a forward-thinking culture that supports continuous school development. Inquiry involves actively seeking information, feedback, and insights from staff and stakeholders to make informed decisions, address challenges, and promote a culture of reflective practice and continuous learning within the school. Advocacy is the commitment to championing teachers' needs, student welfare, and school resources, ensuring a supportive environment that promotes educational success and well-being for all members of the school community. Conflict refers to the approach leaders take to address and manage disagreements

or tensions within the school, aiming to resolve issues constructively and maintain a positive, collaborative environment. Making decisions involves evaluating options and choosing effective courses of action that align with the school's goals and values, while considering the input of staff and stakeholders to foster trust and shared responsibility. Critique involves providing constructive feedback and thoughtful analysis to improve practices, encourage professional growth, and uphold high standards within the school community. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is teacher morale. It has three indicators namely: rationality, belongingness, and identification (Brion, 2015). In this study, rationality refers to teachers' ability to approach challenges logically and calmly, grounded in clear thinking and practical reasoning, which contributes to a stable, positive work attitude and resilience in the school environment. Belongingness is the sense of connection and inclusion that teachers feel within their school community, fostering positive relationships and a supportive atmosphere that enhances job satisfaction and commitment. Identification refers to the sense of personal and professional alignment teachers feel with the values, goals, and culture of the school, which strengthens their engagement, motivation, and overall satisfaction with their role.

1.4. Statement of the Problem —This study determined the relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher

morale in public secondary schools of Davao del Norte Division. More specifically, it answered the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of administrative styles of school heads as perceived by public secondary teachers in terms of:
 - (1) initiative
 - (2) inquiry
 - (3) advocacy
 - (4) conflict;
 - (5) making decisions; and
 - (6) critique

Fig. 1. Theoretical Conceptual Framework of the Study

- (2) What is the extent of morale of public secondary teachers in terms of:
 - (1) rationality;
 - (2) belongingness; and
 - (3) identification
- (3) . Is there a significant relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale?
- (4) Which domains of administrative styles of school heads significantly influence the teacher morale?

1.5. *Hypotheses* —Ho1. There is no significant relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. Ho2. None of the domains of administrative styles of school heads significantly influence the teacher morale.

In this academic journey, it was claimed that school heads play a central role in shaping teacher morale. By examining this relationship, the study provided valuable insights into how specific administrative approaches affected teacher morale. This study offered valuable benefits to pertinent stakeholders, specifically DepEd officials, school heads, teachers, and future researchers. It provided these stakeholders with insights that could be utilized to formulate policies, design programs, implement interven-

tions, aimed at reinforcing the administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale.

Teachers – This undertaking was highly significant for teachers as it highlighted how leadership approaches could influence their work environment, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. By understanding this relationship, teachers could gain insight into how different administrative styles affect their motivation, sense of value, and professional growth. This knowledge would empower teachers to advocate for leadership practices that create a more supportive and collaborative atmosphere, where their contributions are recognized, and their professional needs are met. Furthermore, the study could serve as a catalyst for open dialogue be-

tween teachers and school heads, fostering a stronger partnership that ultimately improves both teacher morale and student outcomes.

School Heads – This study held profound significance for school heads as it offered valuable insights into how their leadership approach directly impacts the morale of their teaching staff. By understanding this dynamic, school heads could identify which leadership practices foster a positive and supportive school environment, leading to improved teacher satisfaction, productivity, and retention. This knowledge would allow school leaders to adopt strategies that enhance teacher engagement, reduce burnout, and build a more collaborative and cohesive team. Important terms were defined con-

ceptually and operationally in order to provide a clear view of the content of this study. These terms served as point of reference to the readers.

Administrative Styles – These refer to the distinct approaches and strategies employed by the school heads in managing school operations, leading staff, and making decisions to achieve organizational goals effectively. In this study, it refers to initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decisions, and critique. **Teacher Morale** – It refers to the overall level of confidence, enthusiasm, and satisfaction teachers feel about their work, which influences their motivation, performance, and commitment to their roles. In this study, it refers to rationality, belongingness, and identification.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the methodological dimension of the study is presented, encompassing the research design, participants, research instruments, data collection procedures, and the analytical approach to be utilized in this investigation.

2.1. Research Design—This research utilized a quantitative methodology, specifically applying a descriptive correlational design. Quantitative research involves gathering numerical data, which is then analyzed using mathematical and statistical methods to clarify and provide insights into particular issues or phenomena (Adedoyin, 2020). In descriptive correlational studies, the focus is on describing the variables and identifying the natural relationships that exist between them (Creswell Creswell, 2018). In particular, descriptive research is a methodological approach that seeks to depict the characteristics of a phenomenon or subject under investigation. In scientific inquiry, it serves as a foundational tool for researchers aiming to observe, record, and analyze the intricate details of a particular topic. This method provides a rich and detailed account that aids in understanding, categorizing, and interpreting the subject matter (Singh, 2023). Conversely, a

correlational study aims to ascertain whether there is a connection between two variables. This entails investigating whether changes in one variable are associated with corresponding increases or decreases in the other (Bhandari, 2023). In the context of this study, it was considered descriptive-correlational research because it described and examined the relationship between two key variables: the administrative styles of school heads and the morale of teachers. The descriptive aspect of the study focused on providing an in-depth account of the various leadership styles employed by school heads and how they were perceived by teachers in terms of morale. The correlational aspect, on the other hand, explored the potential relationships between these variables, aiming to determine whether and to what extent the different administrative styles influence teacher morale. By gathering and analyzing data on these variables, the study offered valuable insights into

how administrative styles impact teacher morale in the context of public secondary schools.

2.2. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are crucial in research to protect the rights, well-being, and dignity of participants while ensuring the integrity and credibility of the study. The researcher adhered to principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, and non-maleficence, ensuring participants were fully aware of the research’s nature, risks, and purpose before agreeing to take part. In fact, ethical guidelines also protected vulnerable populations from exploitation and ensured that research findings were reported truthfully, without manipulation or falsification. Therefore, all ethical considerations and the scope of the study were explicitly detailed in this quantitative research. These concerns largely arose from the methodology employed. The study followed the ethical guidelines established by the college Ethics Review Committee, particularly regarding the study’s population and data, which include but were not limited to:

Social Value – This undertaking held significant social value as it addressed critical factors influencing the educational environment. It provided insights that can enhance the overall effectiveness of schools. The findings of the study had the potential to inform policy decisions and professional development programs within the Davao del Norte Division, ensuring that school leadership was aligned with the needs and well-being of teachers. Ultimately, the study contributed to the broader goal of improving educational quality by fostering a supportive and dynamic school culture that benefitted teachers, students, and the wider community.

Informed Consent Process – The informed consent process was designed to uphold the ethical principles of transparency, autonomy, and respect for all participants. Before participating, teachers and school heads were provided with a detailed explanation of the study’s objec-

tives, significance, procedures, and the expected time commitment. This was done through an easy-to-understand information sheet and verbal communication to ensure comprehension. The consent form explicitly stated that participation was entirely voluntary, and participants had the right to decline or withdraw at any stage of the study without any repercussions. Additionally, participants were assured that their responses remained confidential and anonymous, and data were used solely for research purposes, stored securely to prevent unauthorized access. The researcher also addressed any questions or concerns from participants before obtaining their signed consent. This thorough and ethical approach to informed consent ensured that participants were fully aware of their rights and the scope of their involvement, fostering trust and integrity throughout the research process.

Vulnerability of Research Participants – The study acknowledged the potential vulnerabilities of its participants, particularly given the sensitive nature of examining leadership practices and their impact on teacher morale. Teachers may feel apprehensive about sharing their perspectives, especially if they believed their responses could affect their professional relationships or standing within the school community. To address these concerns, the researcher prioritized creating a safe and non-judgmental environment, ensuring that all participants feel comfortable and secure in sharing their honest insights. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, with no identifying information linked to individual responses. Participants were also reminded that their involvement was entirely voluntary, and they could withdraw at any time without facing any consequences. Furthermore, the researcher approached data collection with cultural sensitivity and a deep respect for the local educational context. By adhering to rigorous ethical standards and fostering an atmosphere of trust, the study minimized any potential risks and protect the rights and well-

being of all participants.

Risks, Benefits and Safety – This academic inquiry carefully considered the potential risks, benefits, and safety of its participants to ensure an ethical and constructive research process. Minimal risks were anticipated, primarily relating to participants’ potential discomfort in discussing leadership practices or morale issues. To mitigate this, the researcher created a respectful and supportive environment, emphasizing the voluntary nature of participation and ensuring confidentiality and anonymity to protect participants’ privacy. The benefits of the study, however, were significant. By identifying how various administrative styles influence teacher morale, the research provided actionable insights that could inform leadership development programs and policy improvements, ultimately fostering a more supportive and effective educational environment. Participant safety was a top priority throughout the study, with secure data handling protocols in place to prevent unauthorized access or misuse of information.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information – The study placed a high priority on ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of all participant information. To protect the identities and responses of participants, all data collected were anonymized, with identifying details removed during data processing. The respondents were assigned unique codes to ensure that their responses cannot be traced back to them. All data were securely stored in password-protected digital files and, if necessary, in locked physical storage to prevent unauthorized access. Access to the data was strictly limited to the researcher and, if applicable, the academic advisor, ensuring the information remains confidential. Participants were also informed that their responses were used solely for research purposes and presented only in aggregated form in the final report. By adhering to these measures, the study upheld ethical standards, fosters trust among participants, and guaranteed that their privacy

was respected throughout the research process.

Justice – The study upheld the principle of justice, emphasizing fairness and equity throughout its research process. It ensured that all participants, regardless of their roles, schools, or professional backgrounds, had equal opportunities to contribute, enabling diverse and representative perspectives on administrative styles and their influence on teacher morale. The recruitment process was designed to prevent favoritism or exclusion, ensuring that no group bore a disproportionate burden or was unfairly excluded. Moreover, the study produced findings that benefit all stakeholders, including teachers, school heads, and the wider educational community. By exploring leadership practices that enhance teacher morale, the research drove equitable improvements in educational settings across the division. This dedication to fairness and the equitable sharing of the study’s benefits underscores its ethical integrity and ensures the outcomes meaningfully address the needs of all participants and stakeholders.

Transparency – The research prioritized transparency throughout its entire process. Participants received comprehensive and clear explanations regarding the study’s aims, objectives, methodology, and anticipated outcomes prior to their participation. This included detailing the procedures for data collection, analysis, and utilization, along with assurances of confidentiality and adherence to ethical standards. Stakeholders were regularly updated to keep them informed of the study’s developments. Furthermore, the results were reported accurately and impartially, ensuring that the findings reflect the data without distortion. By promoting open communication and ensuring all processes were clearly conveyed, the research-built trust, fosters accountability, and encourages collaboration, underscoring its commitment to ethical practices and active engagement with all stakeholders.

Recruitment – The recruitment process was

carried out in an ethical, inclusive, and fair manner. Participants were chosen using a structured approach to ensure a diverse representation across the schools in the division. The researcher worked closely with school administrators to identify eligible participants, including school heads and teachers who met the study's criteria. Prospective participants were provided with clear and thorough information about the study's purpose, goals, and participation expectations, enabling them to make informed decisions. Recruitment materials stressed that participation was voluntary, assuring individuals that their involvement or withdrawal did not influence their professional standing or relationships. By emphasizing transparency, fairness, and respect for individual autonomy, the recruitment process built trust and encouraged meaningful participation, ensuring that the study captured a broad range of perspectives within the educational community.

Conflict of Interest (COI) – The study was dedicated to identifying and addressing any potential conflicts of interest (COI) to maintain the integrity of the research process. The researcher openly disclosed any personal, professional, or financial connections that could influence the study's design, data collection, analysis, or reporting. This commitment to transparency minimized bias and ensured the objectivity of the research. School heads and teachers were clearly informed about the study's objectives and the voluntary nature of their participation, with reassurances that their involvement did not affect their professional relationships, assessments, or career progression. To further prevent any perceived or actual conflicts, the researcher adopted a neutral position, ensuring that no participant felt pressured to take part. By proactively addressing potential COIs, the study upheld ethical standards, protected the reliability of its findings, and built trust with participants and stakeholders.

Adequacy of Facilities – The study priori-

tized ensuring the availability of adequate facilities to support effective data collection and analysis. Essential infrastructure was in place, including suitable spaces for interviews or focus group discussions, dependable technological tools for gathering and analyzing data, and a secure system for safeguarding sensitive information. The schools participating in the study were consulted to verify that their facilities met the necessary standards for privacy, comfort, and accessibility, creating an environment conducive to participants sharing their insights without distractions or discomfort. Additionally, the researcher ensured that all required resources, such as questionnaires or survey platforms, were functional and available. By ensuring the adequacy and maintenance of these facilities, the study facilitated a seamless research process while adhering to ethical standards of confidentiality and protecting participants' well-being.

Permission from Organization/Location – Securing approval from the appropriate educational authorities and institutions was a crucial step in ensuring that the study adheres to organizational procedures and ethical standards. Before beginning data collection, formal consent was obtained from the Department of Education (DepEd) Davao del Norte Division, along with the approval of individual school heads, to ensure the research aligned with the division's policies and goals. The researcher clearly communicated the study's objectives, methods, and potential benefits to the participating schools and their staff, ensuring that all involved were well-informed and supportive of the research. By obtaining the necessary permissions from relevant organizations and locations, the study moved forward with institutional endorsement, maintaining respect for the schools' leadership and fostering cooperation and transparency throughout the entire research process.

Authorship – The researcher is undertaking a Master of Arts in Educational Management

and was committed to producing high-quality research. The development of the thesis involved multiple revisions, incorporating feedback from both the academic advisor and expert reviewers. The academic advisor, who also collaborated as a co-author, offered valuable guidance in refining the research methodology, data analysis, and overall approach, ensuring that the study adhered to strict academic criteria. In addition, the researcher was devoted to upholding the ethical standards set by the Ethics Review Committee, ensuring the integrity of the research process, safeguarding the rights of participants, and promoting transparency.

2.3. Research Respondents —This study involved 190 public secondary school teachers who were invited to participate and provide responses. The sample size was determined using the Slovin Formula, based on a population of 365 teachers from Grade 7 to Grade 10 with at least three years of teaching experience, resulting in a sample of 190 teachers. According to Hair et al. (2018), a minimum of 50 participants is recommended for simple regression analysis, with 100 samples typically being sufficient for most research purposes. Therefore, the inclusion of 190 respondents exceeded the required sample size, ensuring the study's objectives are met. For this study, a probability sampling technique, specifically two-stage cluster sampling, was utilized to select the sample. This method ensures that each member of the population has an equal and independent chance of being included in the sample. Cluster sampling is a widely used approach in research, where the population is divided into distinct groups, or clusters, each consisting of unique units that represent

Teacher Morale – The teacher morale questionnaire was adapted from Brion (2015). The tool has a total of 14 items. It had three indicators, namely: rationality (1-3), belongingness (1-5), and identification (1-6). The question-

naire represent exhaustive and mutually exclusive subsets (Thomas, 2020). Since the sample was randomly selected from each designated cluster or division, this qualified as two-stage cluster sampling. In this study, all public secondary school teachers in the Davao del Norte Division were considered for inclusion. For this research, public secondary school teachers from Grades 7 to 10 with at least three years of teaching experience were chosen, as their tenure in the public education system equipped them to assess the administrative styles of their school heads and their own morale as educators. Participants who felt uneasy or uncomfortable with completing the survey questionnaire were free to withdraw from the study at any time, without any pressure to continue. Their decision to withdraw was fully respected, with the study prioritizing the participants' comfort and well-being throughout the process.

2.4. Research Instruments —For data collection, this study used an adapted survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured into two sections: the first section focused on the administrative styles of school heads, while the second section addressed teacher morale. *Administrative Styles* – The questionnaire on administrative style was adapted from the study of Al-Omari (2013). It had a total of 36 items. It comprised the following indicators: initiative (1-5), inquiry (1-6), advocacy (1-6), conflict (1-6), making decisions (1-6), and critique (1-6). The tool was subjected to pilot testing for reliability test leading to a result of .82 which suggested high internal consistency. Below were the scales used to interpret the means of administrative styles of school heads.

naire was subjected to a pilot testing for reliability test and this led to a result of .85 which suggested a high internal consistency. Below was the rating scale of teacher morale.

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The administrative styles of school heads are always evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The administrative styles of school heads are oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The administrative styles of school heads are occasionally evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The administrative styles of school heads are seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The administrative styles of school heads are never evident.

Mean Interval	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher morale is always evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	The teacher morale is oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher morale is occasionally evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher morale is seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher morale is never evident.

The research tool for this study was carefully developed to ensure it effectively addressed the study’s objectives. To ensure construct validity, the instrument was reviewed by a panel of expert validators. The researcher incorporated feedback, suggestions, and recommendations from the advisor, panel members, and validators during a thorough revision process. After these adjustments, the survey questionnaire underwent a pilot test with a sample of thirty (30) public secondary school teachers who were not part of the main respondent group. This iterative refinement process was crucial for ensuring the instrument accurately measured the constructs intended for study.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure —In gathering the data, the researcher followed a strict procedure and protocol. This also meant following the guidelines set by the Ethics Review Committee which protected the welfare of the identified respondents.

Permission to Conduct the Study – After obtaining approval from the Dean of Graduate Studies, the researcher requested permission and endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendents. Upon receiving the approval by means of Ethics Certificate and Endorsement, an official endorsement letter was submitted to

the school heads of the selected institutions. To ensure minimal disruption to regular classroom activities, the researcher coordinated with the school heads to determine appropriate schedules for data collection, making sure that no classes were interrupted during the study. The permission to conduct the study started on February 3, 2025 once the approval was granted from the Dean’s Office and the Ethics Review Committee.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire – Following approval, a schedule was arranged for the distribution of the survey questionnaires. In line with health and safety protocols, the questionnaires were administered in person. Administering the survey possibly commenced on February 10 – 14, 2025 once the permission to conduct the study was granted. This process ensured that the research was conducted with respect to the operational needs of the schools and the academic calendar. The researcher explained the purpose and importance of the survey to the respondents beforehand. Participants were given allotted one hour to complete the survey. Upon completion, the responses were automatically recorded and processed in the system to ensure accurate data retrieval. This approach ensured that partici-

pants had adequate time to respond while maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of their answers.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data – All collected data were carefully compiled, organized, analyzed, and interpreted in a confidential and systematic manner. For the computation, analysis, and interpretation of the data, the researcher sought the assistance of a designated statistician to ensure accuracy and reliability in the results. This collaboration ensured that the data was processed correctly, following established statistical methods, to derive meaningful insights that aligned with the study’s objectives. Additionally, maintaining confidentiality throughout this process was critical to uphold ethical standards and protect participant information.

2.6. *Data Analysis* —For more comprehensive interpretation and analysis of the data, the following statistical tools were utilized.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the study. These are the findings of the problems raised in the previous chapter. They are presented both in the textual and tabular forms.

3.1. *Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Initiative*—Table 1 reflects the administrative styles of school heads

It can be gleaned from the data that all 6 statements reveal an extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: initiating actions that help and support others (3.50), exerting vigorous effort and cause others to join in enthusiastically (3.48), and stressing loyalty and extend appreciation to those who support his/ her initiatives (3.46). The three lowest items according to mean scores are as follows: putting out enough to get by (3.45), driving himself/herself and others (3.43), and

These tools answered the statement of the problem and the hypotheses.

Mean – This refers to the arithmetic average of a set of numbers, calculated by dividing the sum of all values by the total number of values in the set. It was used to measure the level of administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale.

Pearson r – It is a statistical measure that evaluates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. This was utilized to determine the relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale.

Regression Analysis – It is a statistical method used to examine the influence or to predict outcomes or identify trends. This was utilized to determine the significant influence of administrative styles of school heads on teacher morale.

in terms of initiative. It shows that the overall mean is 3.46, in an extensive level. This means that the level of administrative styles of school heads in terms of initiative is oftentimes evident.

seeking to maintain a steady pace (3.42). These items prove that the administrative styles of school heads in terms of initiative are oftentimes evident. The findings indicate that the administrative styles of school heads in terms of initiative are generally practiced at an extensive level. This suggests that school heads frequently demonstrate proactive behavior, exerting effort to support and motivate others. The consistency of moderately high scores across all six indicators reflects a strong inclination toward initiating action and taking leadership

Table 1. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Initiative

No	Initiative	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Initiating actions that help and support others.	3.50	Extensive
2	Putting out enough to get by.	3.45	Extensive
3	Driving himself/herself and others.	3.43	Extensive
4	Seeking to maintain a steady pace.	3.42	Extensive
5	Exerting vigorous effort and causing others to join in enthusiastically.	3.48	Extensive

in advancing school goals. The highest-rated items, such as initiating actions that help and support others and exerting vigorous effort that motivates enthusiasm, highlight school heads' active engagement and their ability to influence others positively through dynamic leadership. Conversely, the items with the relatively lower mean scores, including maintaining a steady pace and putting out enough to get by, point to areas where administrative initiative might be more restrained or routine. While still rated at an extensive level, these lower scores may indicate a need for school heads to further energize their efforts or adopt more ambitious approaches in certain situations. Overall, the data supports the conclusion that initiative as a component of administrative style is a frequently observed and practiced quality among school leaders, contributing to effective school management and organizational progress. The prominence of initiative as a key administrative style among school heads aligns with the perspective of Scott and Manning (2022), who asserted that initiative-taking behavior encompasses active listening, fostering human relationships, motivating others, managing conflicts, and demon-

strating personal adaptability. School leaders who exhibit initiative are able to establish interactive and holistic organizational structures due to their proactive understanding and decisive actions. Fundamentally, the essence of initiative lies in prioritizing the welfare of the organization over personal gain, school administrators underscored that their decisions were rooted in advancing the institution's best interests. In support of the study's findings, Kumar et al. (2024) emphasized that initiative-taking is characterized by strong problem-solving capabilities, creativity, innovation, courage, insight, intuition, and leadership competence. Initiative is seen as the bridge beyond conventional leadership; problem-solving skills serve as foundational requirements for effectively taking initiative. The ability to manage challenges arising from administrative responsibilities reflects systematic, strategic thinking and the capacity to generate solutions, explore alternatives, and act based on profound and well-informed reasoning. Furthermore, Iqbal et al. (2021) highlighted that initiative is a vital component of leadership when viewed through the lens of cognitive structures, belief systems, values, emotional attributes, and

evolving interpersonal dynamics. It fosters autonomy, balances authority, strengthens self-regulation, encourages independence, promotes prosocial organizational behavior, and supports constructive relationships. Complementing this, Lisbona et al. (2021) argued that initiative reflects a form of “real and recognized authority”, one rooted in influence and competence rather than formal hierarchy. In this context, initiative signifies the transition of formal authority into organizational practices, thereby empower-

ing leadership through capabilities rather than positional power alone.

3.1.1. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Inquiry —Table 2 reflects the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of inquiry. It shows that the overall mean is 3.58, at an extensive level. This means that the level of administrative styles of school heads in terms of inquiry is oftentimes evident.

Table 2. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Inquiry

No	Inquiry	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Double-checking what others tell and compliment them.	3.55	Extensive
2	Investigating the facts and positions so that he/she is in control of any situation and to assure that others are not making mistakes.	3.60	Extensive
3	Inviting and listening for opinions and ideas different from his/her own.	3.57	Extensive
4	Taking things at face value and checking facts and positions when obvious discrepancies appear.	3.59	Extensive
5	Looking for facts and positions that suggest all is well.	3.58	Extensive
6	Going along with facts and opinions given to him/her.	3.56	Extensive
Overall		3.58	Extensive

As can be gleaned from the data, all 6 statements reveal an extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to the mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: investigating the facts and positions so that he/ she is in control of any situation and to assure that others are not making mistakes (3.60), taking things at

face value and check facts and positions when obvious discrepancies appear (3.59), looking for facts and positions that suggest all is well (3.58). Meanwhile, the three lowest items are as follows: inviting and listens for opinions and ideas different from his/her own (3.57), going along with facts and opinions given to him/her

(3.56), and double-checking what others tell and compliment them (3.55). These items prove that the level of administrative styles of school heads in terms of inquiry is oftentimes evident. The findings demonstrate that the administrative styles of school heads in terms of inquiry are practiced at an extensive level. This indicates that school heads frequently exhibit behaviors associated with thorough investigation, fact-checking, and evidence-based decision-making. The highest-rated items, such as investigating facts to maintain control and avoid mistakes and checking for discrepancies, reveal that school heads place strong emphasis on accuracy and maintaining a clear understanding of situations before making decisions. Such behavior reflects a leadership approach that values diligence, control, and precision in administrative processes. On the other hand, the lower-rated but still extensive items, like inviting differing opinions and double-checking what others say, suggest that while school heads do engage in inclusive and confirmatory practices, these may not be as strongly emphasized as more authoritative or investigative actions. The relatively lower scores here may point to opportunities for improvement in open dialogue and participatory leadership. Nevertheless, the results overall reinforce the conclusion that inquiry is a key and oftentimes evident component of school heads' administrative styles, supporting well-informed, reflective, and responsible leadership practices. The extensive status of inquiry confirmed the stance of Amels et al. (2020) asserting that school leaders with an inquiry habit of mind value deep understanding tend to reserve judgment, examine a range of perspectives, and systematically pose increasingly focused questions. School leaders who create this kind of culture of inquiry in schools communicate a clear vision on inquiry-based working and stimulate both teachers' inquiry habit of mind and data literacy. Therefore, this study measures the capacity of school leaders to create a culture of inquiry in school by examining the following three aspects: communicating a vision on inquiry-based working, stimulating teachers' inquiry habit of mind, and stimulating teachers' data literacy. Furthermore, Day et al. (2020) highlighted that genuine inquiry, characterized by open-mindedness and a desire to learn, is essential for professional development but can be challenging to implement due to judgmental thinking and avoidance of negative emotion. Inquiry processes are central to building capacity for school improvement and distributing leadership, with principals focusing on key personnel issues and supporting inquiry processes. School heads can promote quality and accountability by maintaining positive relationships with staff, providing training and resources, and encouraging professional growth. Additionally, Aldridge (2023) contended that school leaders who create this kind of culture of inquiry in schools communicate a clear vision on inquiry-based working and stimulate both teachers' inquiry habit of mind and data literacy. Therefore, this study measures the capacity of school leaders to create a culture of inquiry in school by examining the following three aspects: communicating a vision on inquiry-based working, stimulating teachers' inquiry habit of mind, and stimulating teachers' data literacy. The significant presence of inquiry as a leadership approach supports the position of Amels et al. (2020), who emphasized that school leaders with an inquiry-oriented mindset value deep understanding, suspend premature judgment, explore diverse perspectives, and systematically formulate increasingly focused questions. Leaders who foster a culture of inquiry within schools effectively communicate a clear vision for inquiry-based practices and actively encourage both teachers' habits of inquiry and their data literacy. In line with this, the current study assesses school leaders' ability to cultivate a culture of inquiry by focusing on three key dimensions: articulating a vision for inquiry-based work, promoting teach-

ers' inquiry-oriented thinking, and enhancing teachers' capacity for data-informed decision-making. Additionally, Day et al. (2020) pointed out that authentic inquiry, marked by open-mindedness and a genuine willingness to learn, is vital for professional development. However, its implementation can be hindered by judgmental attitudes and reluctance to confront uncomfortable emotions. Inquiry is a central mechanism for building school capacity and enabling shared leadership. Principals play a crucial role by addressing personnel matters, supporting inquiry-driven practices, and reinforcing structures that promote continuous improve-

3.1.2. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Advocacy— Table 3 exhibits the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of advocacy. It shows that the overall mean is 3.67, in an extensive level. This means that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of advocacy is oftentimes evident. It is reflected in the data that all 6 statements reveal an extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: taking the opinions and ideas of others even though he/she has reservations

The extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of advocacy, indicates an extensive level which suggests that school heads often engage in expressing and standing by their opinions while maintaining an openness to the perspectives of others. The highest-rated items, such as accepting others' ideas despite reservations and trying to meet others halfway, reflect a balanced approach to leadership, one that supports assertiveness tempered with collaboration. These behaviors imply that school leaders value both their convictions and the contributions of their colleagues, fostering a more inclu-

ment. By nurturing positive staff relationships, offering necessary training and resources, and fostering professional growth, school leaders enhance both quality and accountability. Moreover, Aldridge (2023) reiterated that school leaders who embed a culture of inquiry communicate a coherent vision for inquiry-based approaches and stimulate both the inquiry mindset and data literacy of teachers. As such, this study evaluates the extent to which school leaders demonstrate these capacities through their ability to lead with vision, inspire reflective teaching practices, and support the effective use of data in instructional decision-making.

(3.70), expressing opinions and ideas in a tentative way and try to meet others halfway (3.69), and feeling that it is important to express his/ her convictions and respond to sound ideas (3.68). Meanwhile, the three lowest items are as follows: standing up for his/her opinions and ideas even though it means rejecting the views of others (3.67), maintaining strong convictions but permit others to express their ideas (3.66), and keeping his/her own position and avoid taking sides by revealing true opinions or ideas (3.62). These items prove that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of advocacy is oftentimes evident.

sive decision-making environment. Conversely, the slightly lower mean scores on items such as standing firm even when it means rejecting others' views or avoiding taking sides suggest that while school heads are generally assertive, they may sometimes adopt a neutral stance to maintain harmony or avoid conflict. This moderation reinforces their role as facilitators of dialogue and unity rather than authoritarian figures. Overall, the findings affirm that advocacy, as an administrative style, is oftentimes evident among school heads, characterized by a healthy blend of conviction, flexibility, and respect for

Table 3. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Advocacy

No	Advocacy	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Keeping his/her own position and avoiding taking sides by revealing true opinions or ideas.	3.62	Extensive
2	Maintaining strong convictions but permitting others to express their ideas.	3.66	Extensive
3	Taking the opinions and ideas of others even though he/she has reservations.	3.70	Extensive
4	Feeling that it is important to express his/her convictions and respond to sound ideas.	3.68	Extensive
5	Expressing opinions and ideas in a tentative way and trying to meet others halfway.	3.69	Extensive
6	Standing up for his/her opinions and ideas even though it means rejecting the views of others.	3.67	Extensive
Overall		3.67	Extensive

diverse viewpoints. The prominence of advocacy as a key leadership approach reinforces the view of Jaffer (2022), who emphasized that advocacy is an essential and increasingly significant aspect of the roles of school counselors and administrators. Students require a safe and supportive environment in which to develop social-emotional skills, guided by trained and empathetic adults. The more opportunities students have to engage in these experiences, the more effectively they cultivate essential competencies. Today’s learners are not confined to acquiring academic knowledge in isolation; rather, through collaborative interactions, they develop empathy, emotional regulation, conflict resolution, critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and perseverance. Furthermore, Hollincheck et al. (2024) highlighted that a vital component of advocacy among school leaders is leveraging the engagement of teacher educators. This in-

volves deepening their understanding of professional responsibilities, expanding their awareness of current issues, research, and best practices, and using data to communicate challenges facing the education system. School leaders are expected to foster a shared understanding, solicit input from stakeholders, and collaborate to pursue common goals. Without the active involvement of educators, parents, and the wider educational community, advocacy efforts may lose their impact. In alignment with the findings of this study, Raymond et al. (2024) noted that school principals play a central role in shaping instructional systems in collaboration with experts such as special education teachers, behavioral specialists, and mental health professionals. Often, multi-tiered systems of support are implemented to address both academic and social-emotional needs of students. This collaborative approach integrates professional exper-

tise to develop effective strategies that serve as the foundation for student-centered advocacy. Through strong leadership, school heads can influence practices and empower teachers to become advocates, driving meaningful change within the school community.

3.1.3. *Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Conflict* —Table 4

exhibits the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of conflict. It shows that the overall mean is 3.45, at an extensive level. This means that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of conflict is oftentimes evident.

Table 4. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Conflict

No	Conflict	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Trying to cut it off or win his/her position.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
2	Trying to find a position that others find suitable.	3.45	Extensive
3	Trying to soothe feelings to keep people together.	3.42	Extensive
4	Seeking reasons for it in order to resolve the underlying causes.	3.50	Extensive
5	Terminating it but thanking people for expressing their views.	3.46	Extensive
6	Remaining neutral or seeking to stay out of conflict.	3.48	Extensive
Overall		3.45	Extensive

It is reflected in the data that the 6 statements reveal a varying result ranging from moderately extensive to extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: seeking reasons for it in order to resolve the underlying causes (3.50), remaining neutral or seeks to stay out of conflict (3.48), and terminating it but thank people for expressing their views (3.46). Meanwhile, the three lowest items are as follows: trying to find a position that others find suitable (3.45), trying to soothe feelings to keep people together (3.42), and trying to cut it off or win his/her position (3.39). These items prove that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of conflict is oftentimes

evident. The extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of conflict falls under the extensive level. This indicates that school heads often demonstrate behaviors associated with managing and addressing conflict constructively. The highest-rated items, such as seeking reasons to resolve underlying causes and remaining neutral or appreciative despite disagreements, suggest that school leaders tend to approach conflict with a problem-solving mindset and a level of emotional maturity. These responses reflect a leadership style that aims to understand different perspectives while maintaining professional relationships and organizational harmony. On the other hand, the lower mean scores, such as soothing feelings to maintain unity or cut-

ting off conflict to assert one's position, indicate a tendency among some school heads to either avoid deeper confrontation or prioritize short-term resolution. While these approaches can sometimes help prevent escalation, they may also reflect hesitation in dealing directly with emotionally charged or difficult situations. Nonetheless, the overall extensive rating affirms that school heads frequently employ effective conflict management strategies, balancing assertiveness with diplomacy to maintain a functional and respectful school environment. The widespread recognition of conflict as a critical administrative concern aligns with the perspective of Hussain et al. (2023), who emphasized that effective conflict resolution entails active listening, creating space for all parties to express their needs, and addressing those needs in pursuit of mutually beneficial, win-win solutions. The integration approach fosters openness and collaboration, allowing stakeholders to share their perspectives and concerns constructively. Similarly, Yin et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of equipping school heads, through the support of policymakers and district education leaders, with skills in conflict management and rational decision-making to enhance teacher efficiency across various dimensions of instructional performance. Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020) noted that conflict in school settings can be mitigated by improving working conditions, such as ensuring the availability of teaching resources, offering supportive supervision,

It is reflected in the data that all 6 statements reveal a moderately extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: looking for decisions that maintain good relations and encourage others to make decisions (4.19), placing a high value on arriving at sound decisions based on understanding and agreement (4.18), and searching for workable deci-

and providing opportunities for innovation and in-service training. These measures empower teachers to become more effective implementers of educational plans. Literature suggests that unresolved conflicts between school leaders and teachers may result in diminished school performance, absenteeism, delays in meeting institutional goals, a toxic work environment, and erosion of trust. However, with appropriate leadership strategies and sound decision-making, conflict can be managed, leading to improved teacher satisfaction and organizational effectiveness. Wainana et al. (2020) further asserted that while conflict can disrupt the teaching and learning process, when managed properly, it can foster constructive relationships and harmonious collaboration between teachers and school leaders. Despite its inevitability, not all conflicts can be fully resolved; however, Azaña (2024) argued that both educators and administrators must be equipped with a clear understanding of the nature and dynamics of conflict. By developing effective response strategies, they can transform conflict into opportunities.

3.1.4. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Making Decisions—Table 5 exhibits the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of making decisions. It shows that the overall mean is 4.13, in an extensive level. This means that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of making decisions is oftentimes evident.

sions that others will accept (4.17). Meanwhile, the three lowest items are as follows: allowing others to make decisions or come to terms with whatever happens (4.16), having the last say and make a sincere effort to see that his/ her decisions are accepted (4.10), and placing a high value on making my own decisions and rarely is influenced by others (4.00). These items prove that extent of administrative styles of school

Table 5. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Making Decisions

No	Making Decisions	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Having the last say and making a sincere effort to see that his/her decisions are accepted.	4.10	Extensive
2	Placing a high value on making my own decisions and rarely being influenced by others.	4.00	Extensive
3	Placing a high value on arriving at sound decisions based on understanding and agreement.	4.18	Extensive
4	Allowing others to make decisions or come to terms with whatever happens.	4.16	Extensive
5	Looking for decisions that maintain good relations and encourage others to make decisions.	4.19	Extensive
6	Searching for workable decisions that others will accept.	4.17	Extensive
Overall		4.13	Extensive

heads in terms of making decisions is oftentimes evident. The administrative styles of school heads in terms of making decisions are extensively practiced. This suggests that school heads frequently demonstrate strong decision-making skills characterized by collaboration, inclusivity, and the pursuit of effective outcomes. The highest-rated indicators reflect a leadership style that values maintaining positive relationships while fostering shared responsibility in decision-making. Specifically, the data shows that school heads prefer to involve others in the process and aim for decisions that are mutually understood and agreed upon, which is essential in building trust and shared ownership within the school community. Although all items still fall under the extensive level, the slightly lower-rated indicators suggest a variance in how school heads balance autonomy with inclusiveness. For in-

stance, while some school heads allow others to make decisions or ensure their own decisions are accepted, others place a strong emphasis on individual authority. This highlights a spectrum of leadership behavior where some leaders lean more toward participative decision-making while others still assert final control when necessary. Overall, the findings indicate that decision-making among school heads is generally characterized by thoughtfulness and a willingness to engage others in the process, reflecting a democratic and relational leadership approach. The considerable emphasis on decision-making as a leadership function reinforces Greene’s (2020) assertion that it is essential for school heads to understand and effectively manage various managerial and decision-making styles in order to lead school personnel efficiently. In this context, implementing systems of checks and

balances, along with comprehensive teacher evaluations, enables school leaders to assign roles and responsibilities more appropriately. Decision-making serves as a critical mechanism for institutional management; without sound decisions, schools cannot develop or achieve their goals. Thus, it is imperative for school leaders to master diverse decision-making approaches and apply them strategically based on situational demands. Through this adaptive process, they can evaluate the effectiveness of different styles on staff performance and institutional outcomes, thereby identifying the most suitable approach to drive educational improvement. Similarly, David et al. (2021) found that principals in high-performing schools foster a collaborative environment by promoting teamwork through celebratory gatherings, consistent staff meetings, ongoing consultations, and the recognition of individual contributions in the decision-making process. Such participatory leadership underscores the importance of inclusive and transparent decision-making in building school success. Anjum (2022) also emphasized that the decision-making styles of school

It is reflected in the data that all 6 statements reveal a varying result ranging from moderately extensive to extensive result. When arranged chronologically according to mean scores, the three highest items are as follows: encouraging and praising when something positive happens, but avoids giving negative comments (3.48), identifying weaknesses in my staff (3.47), and encouraging two-way feedback to strengthen operations (3.45). Meanwhile, the three lowest items are giving others feedback and expect them to accept it because it is for their own good (3.42), giving informal feedback regarding suggestions for improvement (3.40), and avoiding giving feedback (3.38). These items prove that extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of critique is oftentimes evident. The

leaders significantly influence students, particularly those from diverse backgrounds, highlighting the far-reaching impact of administrative choices. In line with this, Shaked (2019) observed that school leaders display variation in their decision-making processes depending on the nature of the issue at hand. For straightforward matters, decisions are made swiftly and efficiently, often producing positive results. However, in more complex situations, school heads tend to deliberate extensively, requiring time for reflection, thorough analysis, and thoughtful judgment. These high-stakes decisions often bring about stress, mental fatigue, and emotional strain, revealing the psychological toll associated with complex administrative responsibilities.

3.1.5. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Critique —Table 6 exhibits the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of critique. It shows that the overall mean is 3.43, in an extensive level. This means that the extent of administrative styles of school heads in terms of critique is oftentimes evident.

administrative styles of school heads in terms of critique are at an extensive level. This indicates that school heads regularly engage in evaluative practices aimed at improving performance and operations. The highest-rated items suggest a preference for constructive and positive feedback, with leaders more inclined to praise accomplishments and identify areas for improvement in a supportive manner. The emphasis on encouraging two-way feedback also reflects a collaborative environment where communication between leaders and staff is open and aimed at mutual growth. However, the lower-rated items reveal certain limitations in the critique practices of school heads. While feedback is given, there appears to be hesitance in delivering informal or potentially negative

Table 6. Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads in terms of Critique

No	Critique	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Encouraging two-way feedback to strengthen operations.	3.45	Extensive
2	Giving informal feedback regarding suggestions for improvement.	3.40	Extensive
3	Identifying weaknesses in my staff.	3.47	Extensive
4	Avoiding giving feedback.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
5	Giving others feedback and expecting them to accept it because it is for their own good.	3.42	Extensive
6	Encouraging and praising when something positive happens, but avoiding giving negative comments.	3.48	Extensive
Overall		3.43	Extensive

feedback, as shown by lower means in statements involving direct criticism or expectation of acceptance. The tendency to avoid feedback in some cases points to a possible discomfort with confrontation or a desire to maintain harmony, even at the cost of addressing necessary areas of improvement. Overall, while critique is evident and valued, there is room for school heads to strengthen their feedback delivery by balancing encouragement with clear, constructive input for professional development. The prominent role of critique in educational leadership reflects the perspective of Congcong and Caingcoy (2020), who emphasized that school heads are instrumental in providing meaningful feedback to teachers, thereby enhancing overall school performance. Effective feedback practices include individualized conversations, reflective techniques, and contextually appropriate strategies. School leaders identified task-level feedback as the most impactful in improving student writing, while person-level criticism was seen as moderately effective, and praise was considered the least beneficial. In sup-

port of this, Goffin et al. (2023) noted that for feedback mechanisms to contribute effectively to school quality assurance, they must deliver accurate, consistent, and comparable performance data. In a similar vein, Miranda (2023) stressed that teachers rely on constructive feedback from school leaders to strengthen their professional practice. Critique plays a vital role in teacher development, as evaluations must not only clarify current levels of effectiveness but also guide educators toward instructional strategies that foster improved student outcomes. Moreover, principals are encouraged to create opportunities for continuous learning, while educational districts should enhance principals' capacity to provide impactful feedback. Zrien and David (2023) further emphasized that relevant and timely feedback equips school leaders with a powerful tool to influence teaching quality and student achievement. When feedback is used effectively, it contributes to the retention of high-performing teachers, an essential asset in sustaining educational excellence. Alga (2021) affirmed that meaningful feedback

enhances teachers' self-efficacy, ultimately contributing to student progress, as it is a cornerstone of both teacher and learner development. Additionally, Kutasi (2023) argued that feedback is a critical element of any effective evaluation system; in its absence, teachers are left without the necessary guidance to understand

what needs improvement and how to achieve it. *3.2. Summary on the Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads*—Table 7 provides a summary on the extent of administrative styles of school heads. It is exhibited that the overall mean of administrative styles of school heads is 3.62, which is in an extensive level.

Table 7. Summary on the Extent of Administrative Styles of School Heads

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Initiative	3.46	Extensive
2	Inquiry	3.58	Extensive
3	Advocacy	3.67	Extensive
4	Conflict	3.45	Extensive
5	Making Decisions	4.13	Extensive
6	Critique	3.43	Extensive
Overall		3.62	Extensive

This means that the extent of administrative styles of school heads is oftentimes evident. Data shows that the six (6) indicators have extensive level. As arranged chronologically, making decision has the highest mean score (4.13). This is followed by advocacy (3.67), inquiry (3.58), initiative (3.46), conflict (3.45), and critique (3.43). These confirm that the extent of administrative styles of school heads is oftentimes evident. The summary of the administrative styles of school heads is categorized under an extensive level. This suggests that school heads frequently demonstrate administrative behaviors aligned with effective leadership practices. The findings indicate that administrators actively engage in various leadership dimensions such as decision-making, advocacy, and inquiry, which contribute to effective school management and the achievement of institutional goals. The consistent results across different indicators highlight the stability and breadth of their leadership approaches in day-to-day operations. Among the six dimensions, making decisions ranked the highest indicating a strong emphasis on collaborative and thoughtful decision-making processes. This is followed by advocacy and in-

quiry, which reflect the school heads' efforts to promote dialogue, understand various perspectives, and support their staff. Conversely, the lower means for initiative, conflict, and critique, although still at an extensive level, suggest areas where leadership practices may be more reserved or selectively applied. Particularly, critique, with the lowest mean may signal a need for more constructive feedback mechanisms. Overall, the data confirm that administrative styles are actively practiced, though with varying levels of intensity across different domains. The broad range of administrative styles demonstrated by school heads supports the assertion of Olayisade and Awolusi (2021), who emphasized that administrative style significantly influences the level of interest and commitment among members of an organization. The ability to effectively mobilize, allocate, and utilize resources, as well as to drive organizational performance, is largely shaped by the leadership approach employed. They argued that the most effective administrative style is one that motivates subordinates, enhances their capabilities, and fosters both efficiency and effectiveness in the pursuit of institutional goals. Further-

more, Shah (2023) described administrators as visionary leaders who excel in strategic planning, offer comprehensive support across various domains, and demonstrate deep respect for all educational stakeholders, including faculty, students, parents, and school board members. Unlike teachers, administrators often operate year-round and handle diverse responsibilities simultaneously. These duties typically include managing budgets, ensuring the equitable allocation of resources, and striving to cultivate academic excellence. Administrative roles also involve key leadership functions, such as shaping curriculum, setting institutional goals, managing timelines and budgets, complying with state mandates, and establishing performance metrics to support educators in achieving both personal and professional success. Similarly, Ada and Mkpá (2020) highlighted that effective

school administration is vital to teaching and learning. It serves as the backbone of any educational institution, directly influencing overall organizational performance. As a core function of educational management, school administration focuses on the practical implementation of educational policies. It involves the systematic coordination and use of human and material resources to achieve the objectives of secondary education in the most efficient and impactful manner.

3.2.1. *Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Rationality*—Table 8 exhibits the extent of teacher morale in terms of rationality. It shows that the overall mean is 4.18, at an extensive level. This means that the extent of teacher morale in terms of rationality is oftentimes evident.

Table 8. Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Rationality

No	Rationality	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Having one of my top priorities is to prepare my students for standardized tests.	4.18	Extensive
2	Being allowed to teach the content I feel is important for students.	4.19	Extensive
3	Standardizing tests is important.	4.17	Extensive
Overall		4.18	Extensive

As revealed from the data, all 3 statements reveal an extensive result. When arranged chronologically, the sequence of the items are as follows: being allowed to teach the content I feel is important for students (4.19), having one of my top priorities is to prepare my students for standardized tests (4.18), and standardizing test is important (4.17). These items prove that the extent of teacher morale in terms of rationality is oftentimes evident. The extent of teacher morale in terms of rationality is classified as an extensive level. This indicates that

teachers generally experience a strong sense of professional logic and reason in their roles, particularly in how they approach instructional responsibilities and academic priorities. Rationality as a dimension of morale reflects teachers' alignment between personal teaching values and institutional expectations, which is crucial for maintaining motivation and satisfaction in their profession. The data show that teachers feel empowered when they are allowed to teach content, they find meaningful underscoring the importance of instructional autonomy. The empha-

sis on preparing students for standardized tests and recognizing the value of such assessments further illustrate a balanced perception of external accountability and internal commitment. These consistently high scores affirm that teachers maintain a rational and purposeful outlook toward their duties, which supports sustained engagement and a positive work environment. The prevailing emphasis on rationality supports the perspective of Robbins (2022), who argued that rationality is closely tied to teachers' perception of job appropriateness where their role expectations align with the institutional goals they are expected to fulfill. The concept of bounded rationality centers on understanding the reasoning behind teachers' (and students') actions, particularly through the lens of cognitive processes. This theory posits that teacher thinking and behavior are shaped by the inherent limitations of human perception and cognition. Faced with the complexities of classroom dynamics, teachers simplify their environment to a manageable level, making decisions that are satisfactory rather than optimal. Their actions are thus guided by how they interpret and define their teaching context. Similarly, Gigerenzer (2024) described rationality more broadly as a

behavioral approach aimed at achieving specific goals within the constraints of a given context. This perspective emphasizes that both goals and situational constraints must be clearly defined, as this distinction differentiates between fully rational behavior and bounded rationality. At the core of this concept is the idea that rational behavior is rooted in reasoned decision-making. Geven et al. (2021) further highlighted that teachers engage in goal-setting, instructional planning, and the anticipation of student outcomes, activities that are indicative of bounded rationality in practice. Through this process, teachers manage and navigate classroom complexities, using their expectations to guide their interactions. These expectations shape how teachers relate to individual students, groups, or entire classes, resulting in differentiated behavior that reflects a rational alignment with their perceived goals and classroom realities.

3.2.2. *Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Belongingness*—Table 9 exhibits the extent of teacher morale in terms of belongingness. It shows that the overall mean is 4.25, in a very extensive level. This means that the extent of teacher morale in terms of belongingness is always evident.

Table 9. Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Belongingness

No	Belongingness	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Knowing how to prepare my students for standardized tests.	4.23	Very Extensive
2	Knowing exactly what my students need to learn.	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Feeling that teaching is a rewarding career.	4.30	Very Extensive
4	Having enough time to teach what I feel is important.	4.28	Very Extensive
5	Being adequately compensated for my job.	4.20	Very Extensive
Overall		4.25	Very Extensive

It can be gleaned from the data that all 5 statements reveal an extensive result. Of which, the three (3) items which have the highest mean score are as follows: feeling that teaching is a rewarding career (4.30), having enough time to teach what I feel is important (4.28), and knowing exactly what my students need to learn (4.25). Meanwhile, knowing how to prepare my students for standardized tests (4.23) and being adequately compensated for my job (4.20) are the items with low mean scores. These items prove that the extent of teacher morale in terms of belongingness is oftentimes evident. The extent of teacher morale in terms of belongingness is interpreted as a very extensive level. This indicates that teachers consistently experience a strong sense of connection, purpose, and fulfillment in their professional roles. A high level of belongingness is a significant contributor to morale, as it reflects feelings of value, reward, and alignment with the mission of teaching. This result suggests that teachers feel closely integrated into their school communities and are deeply committed to their roles. The highest-rated items include feeling that teaching is a rewarding career, having enough time to teach what they feel is important, and knowing exactly what their students need to learn. These indicate a high degree of clarity and satisfaction in their instructional responsibilities. On the other hand, knowing how to prepare students for standardized tests and being adequately compensated received slightly lower, though still extensive, ratings. These findings imply that while teachers strongly feel a sense of purpose and belonging, areas related to assessment preparation and compensation may still warrant attention to sustain and further enhance teacher morale.

As shown from the data, all 6 statements reveal a very extensive result. Of which, the three (3) items which have the highest mean score are as follows: effectively teaching is recog-

The very extensive status of belongingness affirmed the viewpoints of Pardede et al. (2021) revealing that the characteristics of co-teaching relationship appear to be close to a teacher's sense of belonging at work, such as feeling accepted, supported and respected by a colleague. Gorkemoglu and Solhi (2023) highlighted that teachers with a strong sense of belonging in their immediate working environment have a better overall level of well-being and motivation. Moreover, teachers with a strong sense of belonging can enhance a school climate that supports children's sense of belonging. As Pesonen, Rytivaara et al. (2020) found, teachers' workplace belonging is contingent on their relationships with colleagues, the school climate, and leadership. Teachers who enjoy respectful and trusting relationships with colleagues feel valued and accepted and support each other professionally. This enhances their belongingness to the school and job satisfaction. On the other hand, negative relationships at work can cause emotional exhaustion and negatively affect job satisfaction. Similarly, Bjorklund, Warstadt and Daly (2021) found belongingness, relational trust, and self-efficacy positively associated with well-being. Teachers experience a stronger sense of belonging if their values align with the school's and when they feel respected by students.

3.2.3. Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Identification —Table 10 showcases that the extent of teacher morale in terms of identification. It shows that the overall mean is 4.17 which is in an extensive level. This means that extent of teacher morale in terms of identification is oftentimes evident.

nized (4.19), allowing me to attend conferences (4.18), and encouraging me to further my education (4.17). Meanwhile, the items with the low mean scores are feeling needed (4.16), having

Table 10. Extent of Teacher Morale in Terms of Identification

No	Identification	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Being satisfied with my school’s mission statement.	4.15	Extensive
2	Effectively teaching is recognized.	4.19	Extensive
3	Feeling needed.	4.16	Extensive
4	Allowing me to attend conferences.	4.18	Extensive
5	Encouraging me to further my education.	4.17	Extensive
6	Having time to collaborate with my colleagues.	4.16	Extensive
Overall		4.17	Extensive

time to collaborate with my colleagues (4.16), and being satisfied with my school’s mission statement (4.15). These items serve as proofs that the extent of teacher morale in terms of identification is oftentimes evident. The extent of teacher morale in terms of identification indicates an extensive level. This means that teachers frequently experience a strong connection to their professional identity and feel aligned with the goals and values of their institution. High levels of identification reflect teachers’ sense of being valued, supported in their professional growth, and recognized for their contributions. Such perceptions contribute positively to their morale and motivation within the educational setting. The three highest-rated items, effective teaching is recognized, being allowed to attend conferences, and being encouraged to further their education, suggest that teachers feel affirmed and professionally supported by their institutions. Meanwhile, items such as feeling needed, having time to collaborate with colleagues, and satisfaction with the school’s mission statement, though slightly lower, still fall within the extensive range. These findings underscore the importance of continued efforts in fostering a supportive, collaborative, and professionally enriching environment that strengthens teachers’ identification with their roles and

institutions. The prominent status of identification supports the view of Jackson et al. (2022), who found that professional identification plays a mediating role between psychological distress and teaching satisfaction. This suggests that fostering a strong professional identity among teachers should be a strategic priority. The shaping and management of teachers’ professional identities are essential to understanding how educational systems function. Governments and institutions often influence identity formation through discourse, using it as a mechanism of control. This process connects teachers’ professional identity to their work roles, thereby impacting both the structure of the state and the functioning of public education. In alignment with the findings of this study, Titu (2019) emphasized that teacher identity encompasses how educators perceive themselves and their roles in the classroom. It is rooted in core beliefs about teaching and the teaching profession, and it continuously evolves in response to both personal and professional experiences. The literature on teacher identity highlights that personal history and professional encounters significantly influence the development of teachers’ identities. However, these experiences are not formed in isolation; they are interpreted within specific sociocultural and institutional contexts

and shaped through engagement with a community of practice. Similarly, Lobaugh (2024) reinforced that teacher identity is deeply embedded in the values, beliefs, and practices that guide educators' engagement, commitment, and professional behavior both inside and outside the classroom. Research indicates that prior experiences play a crucial role in shaping teacher identity, which in turn influences pedagogical decisions. Consequently, there exists a reciprocal relationship: experiences mold teacher identity, and that identity, in turn, shapes future experiences and instructional practices.

3.3. *Summary on the Extent of Teacher Morale*—Table 11 provides the summary on the extent of teacher morale. It is exhibited that the overall mean of the digital competency of teachers is 4.20, which is in a very extensive level. This means that the extent of teacher morale is very evident. Data show that the three (3) indicators have varying results ranging from extensive to very extensive level. As arranged chronologically, belongingness has the highest mean score (4.25). This is followed by rationality (4.18), and identification (4.17). These serve as proofs that the extent of teacher morale is very extensive.

Table 11. Summary on the Extent of Teacher Morale

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Rationality	4.18	Extensive
2	Belongingness	4.25	Very Extensive
3	Identification	4.17	Extensive
Overall		4.20	Very Extensive

The summary of the extent of teacher morale indicates a very extensive level. This result implies that teacher morale is highly evident across the different dimensions assessed. A high level of morale suggests that teachers generally feel positive, motivated, and supported in their roles, which can enhance their professional performance and commitment to educational goals. The data reveal that among the three indicators of teacher morale, belongingness ranked the highest, followed by rationality and identification. The dominance of belongingness suggests that teachers most strongly value feeling accepted, respected, and emotionally connected to their school communities. Although rationality and identification scored slightly lower, they still fall within the extensive level, reflecting teachers' satisfaction with their professional responsibilities and their sense of recognition within the organization. These findings confirm that all aspects of teacher morale are well-

supported, with belongingness as a particularly strong contributing factor. The highly elevated status of teacher morale aligns with the perspective of Opperman et al. (2021), who noted that high levels of teacher morale are characterized by enthusiasm for teaching and optimism regarding student progress. However, a substantial body of research indicates that teacher morale is often adversely affected by the growing demands placed on educators, which in turn negatively influences their performance. Teachers are frequently confronted with a multitude of challenges that hinder their capacity to effectively deliver instruction and manage classroom activities. Similarly, Sivakumar and Arun (2019) emphasized that teacher morale is shaped by job satisfaction, self-perception, emotional well-being, and the extent to which their professional needs are supported within the school environment. Teachers' perceptions of their roles and the organizational climate

are critical determinants of their morale. It is widely acknowledged that teacher morale plays a crucial role in establishing a positive and productive learning environment. Furthermore, morale is considered an integrative construct that encompasses both individual experiences and group dynamics within the workplace. When morale is high, teachers demonstrate greater enthusiasm and are more likely to perform at their full potential to help the school fulfill its goals and mission. Mutesasira and Bantwini (2022) further affirmed that the delivery of quality education is closely tied to teacher morale, as it directly and indirectly affects teaching effectiveness. Morale and productivity are interdependent, and both are essential for the successful fulfillment of teachers' responsibilities. Enhancing teacher morale benefits not only the educators themselves but also the students

and the school as a whole. High teacher morale contributes to improved student achievement, while low morale can lead to decreased productivity and increased risk of teacher burnout.

3.4. *Significance of the Relationship Between Administrative Styles of School Heads and Teacher Morale*—Presented in Table 12 are the data on the significance of the relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. Reflected in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The overall r-value of .530 with a p-value of <0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means that there is a significant relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. This shows that the administrative styles of school heads are correlated with teacher morale.

Table 12. Administrative Styles of School Heads

Indicators	Dependent Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
Initiative	Teacher Morale	0.528	0.000	Rejected
Inquiry	Teacher Morale	0.534	0.000	Rejected
Advocacy	Teacher Morale	0.537	0.000	Rejected
Conflict	Teacher Morale	0.523	0.000	Rejected
Making Decisions	Teacher Morale	0.539	0.000	Rejected
Critique	Teacher Morale	0.521	0.000	Rejected
Overall	Teacher Morale	0.530*	0.000	Rejected

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.*

Doing a pairwise correlation among the measures of both variables, it can be gleaned that initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique revealed computed r-values of 0.528, 0.534, 0.537, 0.523, 0.539, and 0.521 respectively with p-values which are less than 0.05 in the level of significance. This implies that as initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique increase, the teacher moral also increases. The findings reveal as significant relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05

level of significance, and the overall r-value of 0.530 with a p-value <0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This statistical result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale, implying that the way school heads manage their roles and interact with their staff has a measurable impact on the morale of teachers. The positive correlation signifies that as administrative practices align with certain leadership behaviors, teachers are more likely to experience higher morale. When examining the individual components of admin-

istrative styles through pairwise correlation, the data show that all six aspects, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decisions, and critique, demonstrated significant correlations with teacher morale. The computed r-values ranged from 0.521 to 0.539, all with p-values below 0.05. These results suggest that as each of these administrative practices increases, teacher morale also tends to rise. For example, a school head who is more proactive (initiative), communicative (inquiry), supportive (advocacy), fair in conflict resolution, decisive, and constructive in critique is likely to foster a more motivated and satisfied teaching staff. This highlights the importance of effective leadership in influencing teacher well-being and professional satisfaction. The findings of this study are consistent with Mangin (2021), who emphasized that recognizing the efforts and accomplishments of school staff is a key strategy administrators can use to boost morale and demonstrate support. Such recognition may take various forms and can be delivered in both formal and informal settings. Similarly, Morris et al. (2020) noted that staff members who feel appreciated by school leaders are more inclined to exceed job expectations and make meaningful contributions to the overall school community. Erichsen and Reynolds (2020) further argued that involving teachers in school-wide decision-making is another ef-

One unit change in initiative will lead to 533 unit change in the teacher morale if the other predictor is at “0”. In the same way, one unit change in inquiry will lead to .539 unit change in teacher morale if the other predictor is at “0”. Also, one unit change in advocacy will lead to .542 unit change in teacher morale if the other predictor is at “0”. Moreover, one unit change in conflict will lead to .528 unit change in teacher morale if the other predictor is at “0”. One unit change in making decision will lead to .545 unit change in teacher morale if the other

fective way for administrators to express their support. When teachers are actively included in the decision-making process, they tend to show greater job commitment, increased motivation, and a stronger sense of trust in school leadership. This participatory approach enhances teachers’ belief that administrators genuinely prioritize their well-being and professional growth. Additionally, Qaralleh (2020) emphasized that principals play a central role in shaping school culture. Through their actions, they establish expectations and set the tone for staff behavior and engagement. Effective school leaders are not only approachable but also maintain a visible presence within the school. Their active leadership encourages other members of the school community to take on leadership roles.

3.5. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Administrative Styles of School Heads on Teacher Morale —Shown in table 13 is the regression analysis on administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. The overall p- value ($p < 0.05$) denotes that the administrative styles of school heads is a predictor of teacher morale. The B values of the independent variable, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique is 0.533, 0.539, 0.542, 0.528, 0.545 and 0.526 respectively.

predictor is at “0”. Lastly, one unit change in critique will lead to .526 unit change in teacher morale if the other predictor is at “0”. Among the six, making decision indicates a higher influence on the teacher morale compared to other indicators. Lastly, the coefficient of determination of r-squared value is also shown in the table which was 0.281 or 28.1 % of the teacher morale is explained by the domains of administrative styles of school heads which are initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique. Hence, the hypothesis that there is

Table 13. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Administrative Styles of School Heads on Teacher Morale

Administrative Styles of School Heads	(Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant	0.536	0.541	7.730	0.000
Initiative	0.533	0.556	7.940	0.000
Inquiry	0.539	0.562	8.030	0.000
Advocacy	0.542	0.565	8.070	0.000
Conflict	0.528	0.551	7.870	0.000
Making Decisions	0.545	0.569	8.130	0.000
Critique	0.526	0.549	7.840	0.000
r				0.530
r²				0.281
F				42.60
P				0.000

no domain in administrative styles of school heads that significantly influences the teacher morale is rejected. The regression analysis on the administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale demonstrates that the administrative styles serve as a significant predictor of teacher morale, as indicated by the overall p-value ($p < 0.05$). The coefficients suggest that for every unit change in these administrative behaviors, there will be a corresponding change in teacher morale, assuming other variables are held constant at zero. For example, a one-unit increase in initiative will lead to a 0.533 unit increase in teacher morale, emphasizing the impact of proactive leadership. Similarly, making decisions has the highest B value of 0.545, signifying that this aspect of leadership has the most substantial effect on enhancing teacher morale. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination (r-squared value) in the table is 0.281, meaning that 28.1 % of the variation in teacher morale can be explained by the combination of these six administrative styles. This indicates a moderately strong relationship between the leadership practices of school heads and the morale of teachers. The regression analysis highlights

that leadership behaviors, such as making decisions and advocating for teachers, directly contribute to teacher satisfaction and motivation. Consequently, the hypothesis suggesting that no administrative style significantly influences teacher morale is rejected, as the findings clearly demonstrate that leadership practices play a crucial role in shaping the morale of educators. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Ilrath and Govender (2021), who highlighted that school leaders possess significant influence over teacher morale. Taylor (2019) similarly emphasized that the administrative styles adopted by school leaders directly affect teachers' attitudes and working relationships. Maintaining high teacher morale is essential, as it is a key factor in achieving greater efficiency and productivity. Within any school system, various leadership styles are present, each exerting a distinct influence on teacher morale. Effective educational management underscores the importance of school administrators not only fulfilling their responsibilities but also addressing the professional and emotional needs of teachers. The level of teacher morale directly impacts the quality of service they provide, particularly

given the broad and demanding roles teachers are expected to perform. Moreover, Kanthap (2022) stressed that teacher loyalty, sense of responsibility, and productivity are closely linked to the overall morale within the organization. When teachers feel valued and supported, they are more likely to display positive behaviors and diligently fulfill their responsibilities. Conversely, in schools where incentives, motivation, and morale are lacking, institutional performance tends to decline, and teachers may experience disengagement and reduced effectiveness. Within the context of this study, transformational leadership theory provides a relevant framework for understanding the administrative styles of school heads and

their impact on teacher morale. This theory emphasizes a leader's ability to inspire, motivate, and support their team in achieving shared goals. Transformational school leaders cultivate an environment characterized by growth, collaboration, and innovation, where teachers feel recognized, empowered, and professionally fulfilled. By promoting open communication, acknowledging accomplishments, and supporting personal development, this leadership style addresses both the emotional and professional needs of educators. As a result, it fosters high teacher morale, builds trust, reduces workplace stress, and nurtures a strong sense of purpose and community ultimately enhancing teacher satisfaction and performance.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings based on the results of data gathered, the conclusions drawn from the findings and the recommendations for consideration.

4.1. Findings—The main focus of the study was to determine the significance of the relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale in public secondary schools. The study was conducted in the selected secondary schools in Davao del Norte Division. There were one hundred ninety (190) secondary teachers who participated in this study. Descriptive correlational method of research was used in this study utilizing adopted research instruments. The said instruments were validated by the panel of experts and subjected to pilot testing before it was made ready for administration. Mean, Pearson Product Correlation of Coefficient, and Regression Analysis were the statistical tools used in analyzing the data. The hypotheses raised in this study were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The extent of administrative styles of school heads is extensive. The data reveals that the administrative styles of school heads are consistently applied at an extensive level, highlighting their

frequent and effective use. This suggests that school heads actively engage in practices such as initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict resolution, decision-making, and critique. Overall, the extensive application of these styles indicates a strong leadership presence that likely contributes to a positive school environment and teacher morale. Meanwhile, the extent of teacher morale is very extensive. The data suggest a high degree of satisfaction and motivation among teachers. This is reflected in their strong sense of belonging, rationality, and identification with their work, which are key indicators of a positive work environment. The high level of morale may lead to improved job performance and greater commitment to students and the school community. It was found out that there is a significant relationship between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale. All domains of administrative styles of school heads are linked with teacher morale. Each domain of administrative style,

including initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, decision-making, and critique, is positively correlated with teacher morale. This suggests that the leadership behaviors of school heads play a crucial role in fostering a motivating and supportive work environment for teachers. More so, it was revealed that all the domains of administrative styles of school heads, namely, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique significantly influence the teacher morale. The analysis shows that all domains of administrative styles, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, decision-making, and critique, have a significant impact on teacher morale. This suggests that each leadership approach plays a key role in shaping the motivation and engagement of teachers within the school environment. The positive influence of these domains indicates that effective leadership in these areas can foster higher teacher satisfaction and performance.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The extent of administrative styles of school heads is extensive which means that it is oftentimes evident. In particular, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique are oftentimes evident. Meanwhile, the extent of teacher morale is very extensive which is always evident. Specifically, belongingness is always evident while rationality and identification are oftentimes evident. Based on the findings, administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale are related. All domains of administrative styles of school heads are linked to teacher morale. Also, administrative styles of school heads significantly influenced the teacher morale. In fact, all domains of administrative styles of school heads, namely, initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict, making decision, and critique significantly influence the teacher morale significantly influence the teacher morale by registering a p-value of .000 which is less than .05 in the level of significance.

This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further, the result indicates that for every unit increase in the six domains of administrative styles of school heads, the teacher morale will also increase. The significant and moderately positive correlation between the administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale supports the foundational principles of Herzberg et al.'s (1959, as cited in Nickerson, 2023) Two-Factor Theory of Motivation. This theory posits that employee motivation and morale are influenced by two distinct categories: motivator factors, which directly foster job satisfaction, and hygiene factors, which are necessary to prevent dissatisfaction. These factors collectively contribute to improved work performance and morale. Within the school setting, teacher morale becomes a key variable linked to the effectiveness of administrative practices. The level of morale in an organization directly impacts teacher loyalty, sense of responsibility, and productivity. Teachers who feel supported and valued are more likely to display positive behaviors and perform their duties with commitment and efficiency. Thus, morale plays a critical role in ensuring effective and efficient school management. Supporting this perspective, Ilrath and Govender (2021) asserted that school leaders possess considerable influence over teacher morale. Likewise, Taylor (2019) underscored that the administrative styles of school heads significantly shape teachers' attitudes and workplace dynamics. High teacher morale should be prioritized, as it contributes to greater efficiency and enhanced school performance. Given the diversity of leadership styles present within educational institutions, each has a unique impact on teacher motivation and morale. In the context of this study, Herzberg's theory is particularly relevant to understanding how the administrative styles of school heads influence teacher morale. School leaders can strengthen teacher morale by addressing hygiene factors, such as fair compensation, supportive working conditions, and job

security, while simultaneously fostering motivator factors, including professional recognition, opportunities for growth, and a sense of accomplishment. By balancing these elements, school heads can create a positive and productive environment that supports teacher well-being and institutional success.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following suggestions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: DepEd Officials – Based on the findings, it is recommended that DepEd officials strengthen capacity-building programs and professional development initiatives for school heads, with a focus on enhancing their administrative styles, particularly in the areas of initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict resolution, decision-making, and critique. Since these domains have been found to significantly influence teacher morale, such efforts can lead to a more motivated and engaged teaching workforce. DepEd may also consider integrating leadership training modules into the continuous professional development framework, emphasizing practical strategies that promote a strong sense of belongingness, rationality, and identification among teachers. School Heads – School heads are encouraged to consistently apply and further enhance their administrative styles, particularly in the domains of initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict management, decision-making, and critique, as these have been proven to significantly influence and improve teacher morale. Given the strong link between these administrative behaviors and the high level of teacher morale, school heads should foster open communication, actively support teacher concerns, involve staff in decision-making, and handle conflicts constructively to promote a sense of belongingness, rationality, and professional identification among teachers. By intentionally strengthening these leadership practices, school

heads may create a more positive and motivating work environment that enhances teacher satisfaction, commitment, and overall performance. Teachers – Teachers may actively engage with and respond positively to the administrative styles of their school heads, particularly in areas such as initiative, inquiry, advocacy, conflict management, decision-making, and critique, as these leadership practices significantly contribute to sustaining high morale. Teachers may foster open communication, provide constructive feedback, and collaborate with school leaders to create a more cohesive and supportive work environment. By recognizing and aligning with the positive administrative efforts of school heads, teachers can further strengthen their sense of belongingness, rationality, and identification within the school community, ultimately enhancing their motivation, job satisfaction, and overall professional effectiveness. Future Researchers – Future researchers are encouraged to further explore the dynamics between administrative styles of school heads and teacher morale by conducting longitudinal or mixed-method studies that can provide deeper insights into causal relationships and contextual factors influencing these variables. Expanding the scope to include different educational levels, geographic locations, or institutional types may offer a broader understanding of how leadership styles affect teacher morale across diverse settings. Researchers may also consider investigating moderating or mediating variables, such as organizational culture, teacher workload, or professional development opportunities, that could influence or enhance the relationship between administrative styles and morale. This can contribute to a more comprehensive framework for improving school leadership and teacher well-being.

5. References

- Ada, I., & Mkpá, M. (2020). Influence of principals' administrative styles on teachers' performance in aba education zone of abia state, nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 4(11), 76–82. <https://rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/Digital-Library/volume-4-issue-11/76-82.pdf>
- Aeslan, G. (2021). School belongingness, well-being, and mental health among adolescents: Exploring the role of loneliness. *Journal of Happiness and Health*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00049530.2021.1904499>
- Ahmad, R., Nawaz, M., Ishaq, M., Khan, M., & Ashraf, H. (2023). Social exchange theory: Systematic review and future directions. *PubMed Central*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9878386/>
- Aldridge, J. (2023). Preparing schools for educational change: Barriers and supports – a systematic literature review. *Taylor Francis Online*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15700763.2023.2171439>
- Alga, N. (2021). The teachers' perception of the usefulness of principal observation feedback and subsequent follow-up through the teacher evaluation process. *Virginia Tech Repository*. <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams>
- Alink, K. (2023). Exploring the concept of school belonging: A study with expert ratings. *Taylor Francis Online*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full>
- Allen, K., Gray, L., & Leary, M. (2021). The need to belong: A deep dive into the origins, implications, and future of a foundational construct. *SpringerLink*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10648-021-09633-6>
- AlOmari, A. A. (2013). The relationship between decision making styles and leadership styles among public schools principals (russaifa education district, jordan). *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Amazan, A. (2024). Servant leadership practices, school heads' decision-making skills, and teachers' job satisfaction. *EJournals.ph*. <https://ejournals.ph/article>
- Amels, J., Kruger, M., Suhre, C., & van Veen, K. (2020). The effects of distributed leadership and inquiry-based work on primary teachers' capacity to change. *PURE*. <https://pure.rug.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/166158375/>
- Anjum, Z. (2022). A study on decision making of head teachers at school level. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372053307>
- Arslan, G. (2021). School belongingness, well-being, and mental health among adolescents: Exploring the role of loneliness. *Journal of Happiness and Health*. <https://www.journalofhappinessandhealth.com/index.php/johah/article/>
- Ascione, L. (2023). Survey highlights troubling teacher morale issues. *eSchool News*. <https://www.eschoolnews.com/sel/2023/05/31/survey-highlights-troubling-teacher-morale-issues/>
- Azaña, K. (2024). The relationship of school heads' conflict management styles and school performance among public elementary schools in the district of jomalig, quezon. *Scimatic Journal*. <https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/>

- Balyer, A., & Ozcan, K. (2020). School principals' instructional feedback to teachers: Teachers' views. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*. <https://ijci.globets.org/index.php>
- Bauries, S. (2019). Perversity as rationale. *University of Arkansas ScholarWorks*. <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/alr>
- Benti, N., & Tarekegne, W. (2022). The current state of secondary school teachers' morale competence to teach. *DOI*. <https://doi.org/10.1080>
- Bjorklund, P., Warstadt, M., & Daly, A. (2021). Finding satisfaction in belonging: Preservice teacher subjective well-being and its relationship to belonging, trust, and self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journal>
- Boehmer, K. (2021). A qualitative study examining teacher and principal perceptions of the impact of feedback on elementary teachers' sense of self-efficacy. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1398484.pdf>
- Booker, K. (2021). Rules without relationships lead to rebellion: Secondary teachers and school belonging. *ADI*. <https://www.adi.org>
- Brion, S. (2015). *Teacher morale*. Pennsylvania State University. https://books.google.com/books/about/Teacher_Morale.html?
- Buenvinida, L. P., & Tamayo, R. G. (2020). School heads leadership and attributes and teachers' morale: Its implication to school performance. *DOI*. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.76.8507>
- Caoc, M. (2022). Influence of organizational culture on teachers' morale. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research*. <http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/2/IJAMR220221.pdf>
- Chandolia, E., & Anastasiou, S. (2020). Leadership and conflict management style are associated with the effectiveness of school conflict management in the region of epirus, nw greece. *PMC*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8314229/>
- Cioppa, T. (2020). Teachers' perceptions of principal classroom observational feedback and its impact on instructional practices. *Virginia Tech Repository*. <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams>
- Congcong, D., & Caingoy, M. (2020). Feedback mechanisms of school heads on teacher performance. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Converso, D., Molinengo, G., Loera, B., Cortini, M., Sottimano, I., Guidetti, G., & Viotti, S. (2019). Organizational climate and teachers' morale. *SpringerLink*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10833-022-09472>
- Dağ, E., & Akdağ, T. (2023). The relationship between classroom management skills and organizational identification. *Dergipark*. <https://dergipark.org/>
- David, O., Madinah, N., & Godfrey, E. (2021). Instructional supervision practice and effective teaching in ugandan secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2021/March-2021/17.pdf>
- Davis, [(2021). *Descriptive-correlational research study on instructional leadership and teacher development*. Unpublished/online as part of academic research. [researchgate.net+ijisrt.com](https://www.researchgate.net)
- Day, C., Sammons, P., & Gorgen, K. (2020). *Successful school leadership*. ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED614324.pdf>

- Din, M., Malik, H. D., & Afzal, S. (2019). Influence of demographics on self-perceived morale of public and private secondary school teachers. *IJER*. <https://bit.ly/3G3JhUH>
- Donlon, E., McDonald, E., Fitzsimons, S., & Sexton, P. J. (2020). Being and belonging: Student-teachers' contextual engagement in schools. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2020v45n6.6>
- Dotta, L., & Lopes, A. (2021). Identities of teacher educators in higher education: A literature review. *Revistas UPN*. <https://revistas.upn.edu.co/index.php/RCE/article/>
- Doygunel, A., & Koprulu, F. (2022). A study of the roles of school responsibility administrators in increasing the quality of school life through social projects in primary schools. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.202202011>
- Duncan, T. (2020). The influence of principal leadership on literate practices and instruction in a middle school. *Educational Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.62608/2164-1102>
- Erceg, N., Galic, Z., & Bubic, A. (2022). Normative responding on cognitive bias tasks: Some evidence for a weak rationality factor that is mostly explained by numeracy and actively open-minded thinking. *ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S016028962100>
- Erichsen, K., & Reynolds, J. (2020). Public school accountability, workplace culture, and teacher morale. *Social Science Research*. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2019.102>
- Fay, D. (2022). Creating meaning by taking initiative: Proactive work behavior fosters work meaningfulness. *International Association of Applied Psychology*. <https://iaap-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com>
- Geven, S. e. a. (2021). How teachers form educational expectations for students: A comparative factorial survey experiment in three institutional contexts. *ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article>
- Gigerenzer, G. (2024). *From bounded rationality to ecological rationality*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781800370685/book-part-9781800370685-17.xml>
- Goffin, E., Janssen, R., & Vanhoof, J. (2023). Principals' and teachers' comprehension of school performance feedback reports. exploring misconceptions from a user validity perspective. *Lirias Kuleuven*. <https://lirias.kuleuven.be>
- Gorgijevsji, A., Lind, C., & Lagerstrom, K. (2022). Subsidiary strategic influence: The role of subsidiary attention-building activities. *Emerald Group Publishing*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/md-05-2021>
- Gorkemoglu, B., & Solhi, M. (2023). A phenomenological inquiry into prospective efl teachers perceived sense of belonging in school placement. *Revista de Estudios Universitarios*. <https://revistaseug.ugr.es/index.php/portalin/article>
- Greene, M. (2020). Technology, trust, and the flow of quality information: A grounded theory study of decision-making among k-12 education leaders in new york state. *Fisherpub*. <https://fisherpub.sjf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi>
- Grissom, J., Egalite, A., & Lindsay, C. (2021). How principals affect students and schools. *Education Leadership*. [Equalite-Lindsay-How-Principals-Affect-Students-and-Schools.pdf](https://www.educationleadership.org/Equalite-Lindsay-How-Principals-Affect-Students-and-Schools.pdf)
- Grves, N. (2020). Using inquiry, data, and evidence-informed practice to build a responsive and reflexive learning environment. *IR Lib*. <https://ir.lib.uwo.ca/oip/138>

- Haynsworth, S. (2021). Educators on the move: An applied study of literature-based solutions for teacher migration within an exclusive urban school district. *DigitalCommons Liberty University*. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3991>
- Hazi, H. (2024). The trouble with ‘delivering feedback’: Reflections of a supervision scholar. *Journal of Educational Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.31045/jes.7.1.5>
- Henderson, J., & Corry, M. (2020). Data literacy training and use for educational professionals. *Emerald Insight*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content>
- Herzberg, F. I., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. (1959). *The motivation to work (2nd ed.)* John Wiley Sons.
- Holden, D. (2017). Teacher morale in an international school in china: A case study. *Studies in Education*, 3, 129–134.
- Holincheck, N., Galanti, T., & Butler, T. (2024). Promoting teachers’ advocacy and agency for equity in stem education through research and reflection. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382232062>
- House, R. J. (1971). A path goal theory of leader effectiveness. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 16, 321–338.
- Hussain, M., Kalsoom, S., & Qadar, A. (2023). Analysis of conflict management practices and strategies at the elementary school level in district rahim yar khan. *GJIMT*. <https://www.gjimt.ac.in/wp-content/uploads>
- Ikhide, J., Adedapo, O., & Moin, M. (2024). Cognitive diversity and initiative-taking in crisis: A multisource multilevel dual-path model. *SAGE Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/10464964241288555>
- Ilrath, C., & Govender, K. (2021). Factors affecting teacher morale in select independent and public schools in south africa. *Turcomat*. <https://turcomat.org/index.php/turkbilmat/article/download/3317/3947/8769>
- Imakpokpomwan, M., Erhabor, A., & Adeyemi, J. (2022). Principal leadership styles as correlates of secondary school teachers’ work attitude in south senatorial district of edo state, nigeria. *Integrity Research Journals*. <https://integrityresjournals.org/journal/IJET/article-full-text-pdf/149C401E3>
- Imperial, J., Madrigal, D., & Dioso, D. (2023). Temperament types and conflict management styles of school heads in the public secondary schools: An explanatory sequential mixed method inquiry. *Technium Science*. <https://techniumscience.com/index.php/socialsciences/index>
- Ingay, A. (2019). Leadership practice of elementary school heads as determinants of teachers’ morale in davao region, philippines. *International Journal of Management Excellence*, 13(2), August 2019.
- Iqbal, Z., Abid, G., Arshad, M., Ashfaq, F., Athar, M., & Hassan, Q. (2021). Impact of authoritative and laissez-faire leadership on thriving at work: The moderating role of conscientiousness. *MDPI*, 11.
- Jackson, K., Pretorius, T., & Noordien, Z. (2022). The mediating role of teacher identification in the relationship between psychological distress and teacher satisfaction during covid-19. *SAGE Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/00469580221110520>
- Jaffer, A. (2022). The role of school counselors in advocating for social justice for all students during the covid-19 pandemic. *ScholarWorks*. https://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/etd_dissertations/62

- Kachchhap, S., & Horo, W. (2021). Factors influencing school teachers' sense of belonging: Empirical evidence. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext>
- Kanthap, J. (2022). Teacher motivation and morale influencing the effectiveness of bangkok metropolitan administration schools. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1383314.pdf>
- Kapoor, K. (2023). A study on the factors affecting morale of college faculty in darjeeling district. *IJNRD*. <https://www.ijnrd.org/papers/IJNRD2306408.pdf>
- Khan, S., Atta, M., & Gul, M. (2020). Conflict management styles concerning administrative experience of principal at higher secondary school level. *Archives of Palarch*. <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/download/5845/5725/11391>
- Kilag, e. a. (2023). School leadership and its role in fostering academic achievement. *AJSLD*. <https://interpublishing.com/index.php/AJSLD/article/view/1915>
- Kilic, Y. (2021). Comparison of taking personal initiative of public and private school administrators according to the perceptions of teacher. *Dergipark*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/2169427>
- Klinck, K., Thutulwa, N., & Pelsler, A. (2023). Creating a high-performing school management team: Bringing talent to the table for effective service delivery. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles>
- Kozoll, R. (2020). Content versus process: The lifeworld construction of a science teaching identity. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1255609.pdf>
- Krasniqi, R. (2021). Principal's role in supporting teacher collaborative learning. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1323731.pdf>
- Kumar, N., Wang, C., & Liu, Z. (2024). Enabling creativity: The interplay of participative leadership, coworkers' knowledge sharing behavior, and employee's creative idea validation. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>
- Kutasi, R. (2023). Feedback: Unveiling its impact and enhancing its effectiveness in education. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Laksar, A., & Majidi, R. (2024). Unveiling the nexus: The interplay between novice iranian english teachers' professional identity and community of practice dynamics. *SAGE Open*. <https://advance.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.31124/advance>
- Lane, J., Shaw, D., & Scott, M. (2022). Educating and advocating: A professional responsibility for school leaders and school counselors. *DOI*. <https://doi.org/10.4148/2637-4552.1171>
- Lisbona, A., Hayas, A., Palaci, F., & Frese, M. (2021). Initiative in work teams: Lever between authentic leadership and results. *PMC*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Lobaugh, E. (2024). Identity, pedagogy, and change. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1417700.pdf>
- Logroño, M., & Tagadiad, L. (2023). Exploring the role of teaching strategies in enhancing student learning outcomes in the philippines. *EduJournal*. <https://so06.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/edujournal>
- Luijk, L., Kruger, M., & Volman, M. (2019). Promoting inquiry-based working: Exploring the interplay between school boards, school leaders, and teachers. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320804095>

- Magha, N., & Ashu, F. (2023). Principal's managerial skills for conflict resolution in secondary schools in fako division, southwest cameroon. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375254864>
- Mangin, R. (2021). Increasing teacher morale. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1303990.pdf>
- Marquez, M. (2023). Conflict management strategies of school heads in santa cruz south district: Input for a proposed conflict resolution framework. *Ejournals*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=21436>
- Marschall, G. (2022). The role of teacher identity in teacher self-efficacy development: The case of katie. *SpringerLink*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10857-021-09515-2>
- Maynooth, N. (2022). Implementing school self-evaluation: The experience of one school in making the process meaningful. *Mural Maynooth University*. <https://mural.maynoothuniversity.ie>
- Mboweni, L., & Taole, M. (2022). Understanding teacher morale among primary school teachers. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1332258.pdf>
- Mboweni, L., & Taole, M. J. (2022). Understanding teacher morale among primary school teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management*. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ijem.8.1.29>
- Meeks, T. (2020). The relationship between principal leadership style and teacher morale in a rural southern school district. *Digital Commons Liberty University*. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3457&context>
- Miranda, S. (2023). What makes principals' feedback effective? *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1398484.pdf>
- Morris, J. E., Lummis, G., Lock, G., Feguson, C., & Hill, S. (2020). The role of leadership in establishing a positive staff culture in a secondary school. *SAGE Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143219864937>
- Motloug, M., & Lew, C. (2023). Drivers and consequences of strategic leader indecision: An exploratory study in a complex case. *Emerald Insight*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108>
- Mughal, Z., Zafar, J., & Illah, N. (2023). The role of principal as instructional leader: Effects on teaching and learning practices and activities on students' achievement at institutes of sukkur iba university. *PSSR*. [http://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2023\(7-III\)32](http://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2023(7-III)32)
- Muntasira, G., & Bantwini, B. (2022). Motivation reinforcement strategies to improve teachers' performance in high schools: A perspective of amathole east district of south african. *Krepublishers*. <http://krepublishers.com/02-Journals/JHE/JHE-79-0-000-22-Web/JHE-79-1-3-000-22-Abst-PDF/JHE>
- Musengamana, I., Shaoan, M., Namanyane, T., & Chineta, O. (2024). Teachers' perceptions towards decision-making processes: A case study of secondary schools in rwanda. *AJQR*. <https://www.ajqr.org/download/teachers-perceptions-towards-decision-making-processes-a-case-study-of-secondary-schools-in-rwanda-14397.pdf>
- Najarro, R. (2024). Exploring the role of feedback in educational outcomes. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/fedu>
- Newman, S. (2020). Vygotsky, education, and teacher education. *Leeds Beckett University*. <https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/7123/1/VygotskyEducationAndTeacherEducationAM-NEWMAN.pdf>

- Nickerson, C. (2023). Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation-hygiene. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/herzbergs-two-factor-theory.html>
- Nwukor, M. (2023). Connecting principals' leadership, teacher collaboration and students' achievement. *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Practice*. [https://www.ijilpm.com.ng/assets/vol.%2c-5\(4\)-matilda-onyi-nwukor.-c.pdf](https://www.ijilpm.com.ng/assets/vol.%2c-5(4)-matilda-onyi-nwukor.-c.pdf)
- O'Neill, B. (2023). The cognitive and affective components of organizational identification. *Molloy University*. https://digitalcommons.molloy.edu/bus_facpre/11
- Olaso, A., & Baja, R. (2019). Professional accountability of secondary school heads towards quality assurance. *IJARP*. <https://www.ijarp.org/published-research-papers/sep2019/Professional-Accountability-Of-Secondary-School-Heads-Towards-Quality-Assurance.pdf>
- Olayisade, A., & Awolusi, O. (2021). The effect of leadership styles on employee's productivity in the nigerian oil and gas industry. *AMH International Journal of Business Research*. <https://ojs.amhinternational.com/index.php/imbr/article/download/3194>
- Olowoselu, A., Mohamad, M., & Aboudahr, S. (2019). Path-goal theory and the application in educational management and leadership. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 2(2), 448–455.
- Opperman, S., Rotman, S., & van Eeden, C. (2021). Stress, flourishing and intention to leave of teachers: Does coping type matter? *Scielo SA*. https://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2071
- Osondu, H., & Victor, O. (2022). Conflict management and resolution strategies between teachers and school leaders in secondary schools of enugu educational zone, enugu state. *All Subject Journal*. <https://www.allsubjectjournal.com/assets/archives/2022/vol9issue3>
- Otten, S., Wambua, M., & Govender, R. (2021). Who should learn proving and why: An examination of secondary mathematics teachers' perspectives. *International Journal for Educational Mathematics*. <https://www.iejme.com/download/who-should-learn-proving-and-why-an-examination-of-secondary-mathematics-teachers-perspectives-11298.pdf>
- Ozdemir, N. (2020). Principals as instructional leaders: Observation of turkish and math instruction in lower secondary schools in turkey. *National Louis University*. <https://digitalcommons.nl.edu/ie/vol12/iss1/4>
- Özsarı, Ö., & Kara, E. (2024). Organizational identification in diverse groups of teachers. *Dergipark*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/3853161>
- Pardede, S., Gausel, N., & Hoie, M. (2021). Revisiting the "the breakfast club": Testing different theoretical models of belongingness and acceptance (and social self-representation). *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.604090/full>
- Pendharkar, S. (2020). The impact of conflict resolution on staff morale in the irish travel and tourism sector. *Norma*. <https://norma.ncirl.ie/4630/1/shantanurajivpendharkar.pdf>
- Pesonen, H. V., Rytivaara, A., Palmu, I., & Wallin, A. (2020). "teachers' stories on sense of belonging in coteaching relationships". *Springer Link*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10833-022-09472>
- Polite, L. (2020). Teachers' perceptions of the role that school administrators play in their job satisfaction. *Walden University*. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=11069>

- Pressley, T., Marshall, D., Love, S., & Neugebauer, N. (2023). Teacher morale and mental health at the conclusion of the covid-19 pandemic. *Education Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13121222>
- Qamar, Z., & Rashid, M. (2020). Exploration of decision-making styles exercised by heads of secondary schools in punjab and the effects of gender on decision-making. *Education Research International*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1280906.pdf>
- Qaralleh, T. (2020). The role of school leaders in promoting community partnership. *Education Journals*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1291278.pdf>
- Ramani, P. (2019). Whither teacher development – stubborn continuity or winds of change? *Journal of English Language Teaching*. <https://journals.eltai.in/index.php/jelt/article/download/JELT610308/654>
- Raymond, K., Ethridge, E., & Fields, K. (2024). What it takes to be an advocate: Teachers' perceptions of their strengths and challenges. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382760697>
- Reese, D. (2021). School counselor preparation to support inclusivity, equity, and access for students of color with disabilities. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2021>
- Robbins, B. (2022). Grade determination: An exploration of high school teacher cognitive processes. *George Fox University*. <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu>
- Roberts, B. (2022). Teacher morale and practices to sustain morale. *The International Educator*. <https://www.tieonline.com/article/3138/teacher-morale-and-practices-to-sustain-morale>
- Rushton, E., Smith, E., Steadman, S., & Towers, E. (2023). Understanding teacher identity in teachers' professional lives: A systematic review of the literature. *British Educational Research Association*. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/>
- Rytivaara, A., Pulkkinen, J., & Palmu, I. (2021). Learning about students in co-teaching teams. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348932407_Learning_about_students_in_co-teaching_teams
- Saleem, A., Aslam, S., Yin, H., & Rao, C. (2020). Principal leadership styles and teacher job performance: Viewpoint of middle management. *Sustainability*. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/8/3390>
- Saleem, N., Aziz, F., & Quraishi, U. (2019). Morale and job satisfaction of university teachers: A case from pakistani universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1280906.pdf>
- Sarihan, S. (2022). Decision-making of school principals during covid-19 pandemic: A qualitative exploration. *Middle East Technical University*. <https://open.metu.edu.tr/bitstream/handle/11511/95224/>
- Schoildkamp, K. (2019). Data-based decision-making for school improvement: Research insights and gaps. *Taylor Francis Online*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00131881.2019.1625716>
- Scott, B., & Manning, M. (2022). Designing the collaborative organization: A framework for how collaborative work, relationships, and behaviors generate collaborative capacity. *SAGE Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/00218863221106245>

- Shah, Z. (2023). Role of school administrators as instructional leaders in assisting teachers to close achievement gaps: Administrators' and teachers' perception. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375864887>
- Shaked, H. (2019). Systems thinking for principals of learning focused schools. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1228602.pdf>
- Shan, C. (2019). The effect of teacher expectation to students' intrinsic motivation. *Atlantis Press*. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/125969931.pdf>
- Shavuka, T., & Shikongo, R. (2020). Factors contributing to low teacher morale in secondary schools in the oshana educational region, namibia. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368261699_Factors_that_Affect_Teacher_Morale
- Sison Viaro, R., & Ancho, V. (2021). Scale development and investigation of filipino teachers' morale. *Journal of Education Naresuan University*, 23(2). https://so06.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/edujournal_nu/article/view/245035
- Sivakumar, I., & Arun, A. (2019). Morale among school teachers in coimbatore district. *International Journal of Education and Development*. <https://bit.ly/3IIKbaT>
- Skogheim, M. (2023). "i stay because of my students": Urban lower secondary school teachers' experiences of belonging at work. *Nordic Journal of Comparative and International Education*. <https://journals.oslomet.no/index.php/nordiccie/article/view/5533>
- Southworth, J. (2022). Bridging critical thinking and transformative learning: The role of perspective-taking. *SAGE Open*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/14778785221090853>
- Summak, M., & Kalman, M. (2020). A q-methodological analysis of school principals' decision-making strategies during the change process at schools. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1258120.pdf>
- Szumski, G., & Karwowski, M. (2019). Exploring the pygmalion effect: The role of teacher expectations, academic self-concept, and class context in students' math achievement. *ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0361476X18300729>
- Tamunodiepiriye, I., Bedzra, L., & Essuman, J. (2022). Conflict management strategies: A panacea for effective educational leadership. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*. <https://www.gjimt.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/1.-Conflict-Mgmt.pdf>
- Tarraya, H. (2023). Teachers' workload policy: Its impact on philippine public school teachers. *Puissant*. puissant.stepacademic.net/puissant/article
- Tasdemir, M., Iqbal, M., & Ashgar, M. (2020). A study of the significant factors affecting pre-service teacher education in turkey. *ERIC*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ej1280906.pdf>
- Tay, H., & Lam, K. (2022). Students' engagement across a typology of teacher feedback practices. *PMC*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9045682/>
- Taylor, M. (2019). *Administrative involvement with student discipline and teacher morale in mississippi schools*. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1726>
- Tekin, T., & Akin, U. (2021). The relationship between initiative taking levels and problem-solving skills of school administrators. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350794236>
- Titu, P. (2019). Understanding teacher professional identity development: An exploration of secondary science teacher beliefs and practices through reflective practice. *UMN Conservancy*. <https://conservancy.umn.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams>

- Ver, M., Eulen, Krejins, K., & Evers, A. (2020). Transformational leadership, leader-member exchange and school learning climate: Impact on teachers' innovative behaviour in the netherlands. *SAGE Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1741143220932582>
- Viaro, R., & Ancho, V. (2020). Scale development and investigation of filipino teachers' morale. *Journal of Education Naresuan University*, 23(2). https://so06.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/edujournal_nu/article/view/245035
- Wainaina, R., Magoma, C., & Mange, D. (2020). Influence of principals' conflict management strategies on conflict resolutions in secondary schools in murang'a county, kenya. *European Journal of Education and Social Sciences*. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/viewFile/3040/5678>
- Washington, W. (2022). Collaborative practices between general education and special education teachers in middle school inclusion classrooms. *Walden University*. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=12617>
- Werang, B. (2023). School principal leadership, teachers' commitment and morale in remote elementary schools of indonesia. *Hipatia Press*. <https://hipatiapress.com/hpjournals/index.php/remie/article/view/9546>
- Wong, C. E., & Liu, W. C. (2022). Evaluating the teacher professional identity of student teachers: Development and validation of the teacher professional identity scale. *SAGE Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220574221101375>
- Yagan, E. (2022). Professional self-understanding of teachers in different career stages: A phenomenological analysis. *BMC Psychology*. <https://bmcp psychology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40359-022>
- Yalcinkaya, S., Dagli, G., Altinay, F., Altinay, Z., & Kalkam, U. (2021). The effect of leadership styles and initiative behaviors of school principals on teacher motivation. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349801095>
- Yambo, J. (2022). Influence of the principals' decision-making skills on students' academic outcome in public teacher training colleges in nyanza region, kenya. *Journal of Research in International Education*. <https://jrjiejournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/JRIIE-6-3-015.pdf>
- Yang, X., Quynh, N., Wisetsri, W., Qureshi, A., Kumar, T., & Kuo, Y. (2022). Teachers' value consonance and employee-based brand equity: The mediating role of belongingness and self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.900972/full>
- Yin, J., Qu, M., Liao, G., & Jia, M. (2022). Exploring the relationships between team leader's conflict management styles and team passion: From the emotional perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.921300>
- Yip, S. (2024). 'i want to be a part of their conversation': Asian immigrant teachers navigating belongingness in australian schools. *Taylor and Francis*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14681366.2024.2332894>
- Young, E. (2020). African american teachers' perspectives on principals' leadership styles and the influence on teacher morale. *University of South Carolina*. <https://scholarcommons.sc.edu/etd/6131>

- Zhou, J., & Jiang, Y. (2024). Kindergarten teachers' mindfulness in teaching and morale: A moderated mediation model. *OUCI*. <https://ouci.dntb.gov.ua/en/works/7BYkprZ9/>
- Zrien, Z., & David, S. (2023). The impact of school leaders' feedback in enhancing teachers' performance towards school improvement: A single case study among teachers in a private school in dubai. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377851990>